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List of Abbreviations

AAT	All-(factors)-At-a-Time
ANN	Artificial Neural Network
API	Application Programming Interface
BTB	Back-To-Back
CHIL	Controller Hardware-in-the-Loop
COP	Coefficient of Performance
CPES	Cyber-Physical Energy System
DER	Distributed Energy Resource
DPSL	Dynamic Power Systems Laboratory
DoE	Design of Experiments
EV	Electric Vehicle
GFC	Grid-Forming Converter
GFI	Grid-Forming Inverter
GM	Gain Margin
GSA	Global Sensitivity Analysis
HIL	Hardware-in-the-Loop
HLA	High Level Architecture
HTD	Holistic Test Description
HWT	Hot Water Tank
ICT	Information and Communication Technology
IED	Intelligent Electronic Device
ITM	Ideal Transformer Model
JRA	Joint Research Activity
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
LSA	Local Sensitivity Analysis
LV	Low Voltage
ME	Multi-Energy
MG	Micro Grid
MMG	Multi-Microgrid
OAT	One (factor)-at-a-Time
OLTC	On-Load Tap Changer
PCC	Point of Common Coupling
PCES	Polynomial Chaos Expansions
PHIL	Power Hardware-in-the-Loop
PoI	Purpose of Investigation
PM	Phase Margin
PMU	Phasor Measurement Unit
PV	Photovoltaic
PWM	Pulse width Modulation
RI	Research Infrastructure
RES	Renewable Energy Source
ROM	Reduced-Order Model
RTDS	Real-Time Digital Simulator
SCADA	Supervisory Control and Data Acquisition
SA	Sensitivity Analysis
SC	System Configuration
SGAM	Smart Grid Architecture Model
SISO	Single-Input-Single-Output

SuT	System under Test
TC	Test Case
TRL	Technology Readiness Level
UQ	Uncertainty Quantification
VSC	Voltage Source Controller
VSM	Virtual Synchronous Machine

Executive Summary

This document presents a conceptual clarification and a number of methods for *test upscaling* and *domain extension* and the challenges associated with it. Benchmarks developed in the ERIGrid 2.0 project have been used as practical examples to interested users and practitioners for adopting these methods for their research in Research Infrastructures.

The motivation behind this work originates from researchers active in the energy domain attempting to upscale a given test or extend the number of domains represented in their experiment. Typically, a reference model or laboratory setup could be used for a simple experiment but it has its limitations when translating results to the scale of real systems, especially large systems. The challenge here is how to utilise and adapt a given reference setup for delivering results applicable to larger systems and also how to extend the experiment to other domains, especially for tests involving Cyber-Physical Energy System. A typical approach could be to rely on in-house experience for applying appropriate scaling methods, such as replicating some components which might affect the system, leading to significant system change in system behaviour. Since the terminology for upscaling itself can be interpreted differently, which could lead to confusion among researchers.

This research activity first outlines the terminology used for *upscaling* and *domain extension*. *Scalability* and *replicability* are essential characteristics considered for rolling out any given technology to a given market. While *scalability* refers to the capability of a system to modify its scale to accommodate an increase in volume, *replicability* refers to which extent an exact copy of the system can be created. To refine the technical interpretation of *scalability*, the terms *scaling up* and *scaling out* are defined in this work which could help create a common understanding among researchers. By *scaling* a testbed, the physical scale of the system can be reduced, whilst maintaining the integrity and realistic representation of the larger real system. When *scaling out* the number of individual components being investigated are increased, thereby enhancing the capability of the testbed. *Domain extension* means to address also interdependencies of use cases operating across multiple domains throughout a system.

To support the design and assessment of scaling and domain extension tests, a set of analytical methods is identified. The methods are summarised and their connection to the above listed scaling concepts is explained.

Two sets of case studies are presented for *scaling* and *domain extension* in practice by using two benchmarks; an electrical network and a multi-energy network. The first case study illustrates four examples of *scaling up* and *scaling out* in a power system. This case study can realistically represent the current challenges for high Distributed Energy Resource penetration at the Low Voltage systems and also highlight the importance of scaling in the power system analysis. The second case study focuses on domain expansion and scaling up in multi-energy systems. A result of the second case study is that it can be used to identify appropriate testing needs for physical laboratories to prepare the field roll-out of the intended design.

1 Introduction

1.1 Purpose and Scope of the Document

Smart grids and Cyber-Physical Energy Systems (CPEs) are complex systems that need to be safely engineered. This requires analytical and practical validation. Conventionally, the critical elements of energy systems are large-scale monolithic systems, i.e., power plants. In the transition of energy systems to a renewables-driven and smart infrastructure, the generation and flexibility sources are much larger numbers of Distributed Energy Resource (DER). In this multi-purpose and small-to-medium scale setting, methods to assess and validate solutions in the context of increasing scale are needed. In this report, two vectors of this development are considered: the increasing scale of solutions, and their coupling across energy domains.

The challenge of test system upscaling has already been addressed in the ERIGrid project¹ in the context of co-simulation, classifying scale parameters and scaling phenomena. This work aims to continue that work by pushing the focus towards methods for scaling validation of scaled systems and a statistical framework. In practice, approaches for upscaling and domain expansion will be demonstrated via reference scenarios developed in the ERIGrid 2.0 project. This will expand the set of benchmark scenarios and serve as a reference for sensitivity studies. Related to this, it will be analysed which types of sensitivity analysis methods are suitable for test system expansion, be it upscaling via parameter values or component numbers, or via inclusion of further domains. This report is strongly related to uncertainty representation and validation methods (*D-JRA1.2 Methods for Holistic Test Reproducibility*, 2023) and will cover a common pool of concepts and methods with different extensions.

1.2 Structure of the Document

This document is organised as follows: Section 2 describes the background and foundations for the following sections, Section 3 describes the approaches for upscaling. In Sections 4 and 5 case studies applying the approaches are shown. First, a case study for power system scaling up and out. Second, a case study for domain expansion and scaling in a multi-energy scenario. Finally, some conclusions are given in Section 6.

¹<https://erigid.eu>

2 Background

The concepts stated in the deliverable title, “*upscaling*” and “*domain extension*” need to be understood in the context of testing of Cyber-Physical Energy System (CPES). This leads to a range of possible and meaningful interpretations, in particular of the term “upscaling”.

Research in CPES testing and validation has considered the need for testing approaches and testbeds that are capable to represent an increasing scale or complexity of the System under Test (SuT); “*upscaling the testbed*”.

At the same time, technology companies always aim to *scale up the production capacity* (leading to higher factory output or power plant capacity in numbers), or *scale up a technology* (from lab prototype to larger pilot and field test scales), meaning the increased capacity and maturity of single units. In a related concept from an Information and Communication Technology (ICT) background, scaling is an important concept, referring, e.g., to the ability to quickly serve a larger customer base; here, a second scaling strategy is added to *scaling up*: *scaling out* - i.e., to serve increasing demand by increasing the multiplicity of the servers as opposed to their capacity.

The concept of *domain extension* refers to considering the impacts of smart grid-related technology and its flexible operation on other physical infrastructures and sectors.

In this section, we present the background and motivation for investigating scaling approaches in a testing context and formulate the definitions.

This section is organised as follows. Section 2.1 provides the context of scalability and replicability. Section 2.2 outlines scaling strategies and assessment types. Section 2.3 discusses the concepts of domain extension, scale-up and scale-out in power systems. Section 2.4 describes scaling tests and testbed scaling.

2.1 Scalability and Replicability: Context Setting

Scalability and *replicability* are essential prerequisites for successfully rolling out technology to a larger market. They enable or at least reduce barriers to the growth and reuse of the results of R&D and demonstration projects. This is particularly important for companies and utilities, as scaling up and replication can bring high cost, operational and reliability benefits.

Scalability refers to the capacity of a system to modify its scale to accommodate increasing demand volumes.

Scalability has been a topic of research in various contexts, including telecommunication systems, sensor networks, and primarily distributed computing systems. In the context of energy systems, scalability refers to an increase in the total power capacity or load serving capacity.

The term *replicability* refers to the quality of a system that makes it possible to create a copy of it at a different time or place (Wang & Hodge, 2017; Sigrist et al., 2016).

Bottlenecks in the market reach are addressed in a combined *scalability and replicability analysis*. A summary of the factors that comprise this analysis is presented in (Sigrist et al., 2016) and reproduced in Table 1.

Table 1: Scalability and replicability factors (Sigris et al., 2016).

Area	Scalability	Replicability
Technical	Modularity	Standardization
	Technology evolution	Interoperability
	Interface design	Network configuration
	Software integration	—
	Existing infrastructure	—
Economic	Profitability	Market design
	Economy of scale	Macroeconomics
	—	Business model
Regulatory	Regulation	Regulation
Stakeholder acceptance	Acceptance	Acceptance

2.1.1 Explanation of Factors

The technical factors cover the extent to which a technical solution itself is inherently scalable.

Modularity is the basic precondition for scaling up. It refers to whether a solution can be divided into interdependent components. This factor assesses and investigates to what extent a solution is modular (e.g., how easy it is to scale and engineer components independently and whether there are limits on adding components).

The expected *evolution* of the technology on which the solution is based is an important factor for scalability. The progress in underlying technology (e.g., computing power and cost, telecommunication speed and capacity, advanced materials, etc.) should be taken into account when assessing the potential for scalability. The factor technology evolution asks and determines then to what extent technological advances allow increasing the solution size.

Apart from the complexity of the solution itself, the software tools used to deploy it (e.g., simulation models, databases and data management systems, etc.) need to be able to cope with the increased size. Note that this factor can be mitigated by a favourable technological evolution. The factor *software integration* asks and determines then to what extent the performance of software tools is affected when the solution size increases.

The number, complexity and intensity of interactions among the components and with the outside world are addressed via the factor *interface design* and is complementary to the modularity factor. If the interactions grow more than linearly, then the scaled-up solution's performance may be limited. This factor is relevant mostly for the ICT domain, which is relevant for smart grid technical solutions, and is related e.g. to the amount of data that is required to be exchanged and how efficiently these data can be handled.

The factor *existing infrastructure* is related to the pre-existing conditions where the project was implemented, referring to a demonstration project. In a broader sense, it can refer to the compatibility of a technical solution to the current technological environment and to the capabilities supported by the current infrastructure. This factor studies to what extent the current infrastructure creates limits on the maximum size or volume of the solution.

2.2 Scaling Strategies and Scaling Assessment Types

This section develops definitions for the key organising concepts and elements required to discuss how laboratory and simulation-based assessment techniques can support maturity, scalability and replicability.

2.2.1 Technology Oriented vs. Impact Oriented Scaling Assessment

From a technology developer's perspective, the maturing of a given technology is key to technical development and a main reason to perform either simulation-based or laboratory-based assessments. On the other hand, an outside perspective on a new technology would care to ensure that the impact of the technology is correctly assessed, both in comparison with competing technologies, and in the view of the impact of a technology roll-out on the existing infrastructure and existing infrastructure users. These two viewpoints have different scopes of modeling and scaling, which are distinguished in the following as *Type 1* and *Type 2* scaling analyses.

Type 1: Technology Solution Scaling

One perspective in this analysis is related to the inherent limitations of the technical solution itself. Here, the assessment of its scalability and the limitations that may exist for its application. The analysis tries to answer questions such as "How possible is it to implement the same technical solution at a larger scale?", "What technical adaptations and improvements would be required?" and "How to cope with increased requirements and side effects of an up-scaled deployment?" (e.g., large volumes of information, a high number of elements, time delays in communications, interactions between elements etc.).

Type 2: Impact Scaling

Another perspective of the scalability analysis is related to the effects of the solution deployment in the energy infrastructure. Here the aim is to assess the impact of the technical solution on the grid when implemented at a larger scale. This analysis can inform, e.g., technical measures to prepare the existing infrastructure, formulation of grid codes and standards, as well as planning, research and technology roadmap development. In practice, this form of testing and assessment aims to anticipate feedback from field testing and roll-out. This perspective is here complemented with *domain extension*, which considers the impact beyond the power grid. According to (Sigrist et al., 2016), the following have been technical factors that determine whether the developed solution is inherently scalable: modularity, technology evolution (incl. technology maturity), interface design, software integration, existing infrastructure (Table 1).

Usually, the scalability analysis is combined with the replicability analysis. A systematic effort to prepare guidelines to conduct scalability and replicability analysis, based on the experience of European pilot plants, has been made by the European BRIDGE Initiative and the relevant published documents (BRIDGE Horizon 2020 Task Force Replicability and Scalability Analysis, 2019), (Efthymiou, Alacreu Garcia, & Papadimitriou, 2022). The analysis is based on the interoperability layers of the Smart Grid Architecture Model (SGAM) framework. The analyses corresponding to the communication, information and function layers usually include some form of quantification. Within the communication layer, the usual approach is to use simulations to assess the impact of different requirements on the scalability and replicability of ICT systems, i.e., the performance of the systems under different operating conditions as measured through

a set of ICT-related Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) (data loss, latency, error rate, etc.). Generally, the use of software tools for simulations has been reported as an option for assessing scalability in quantitative analyses, so the existence of a simulation model is favoured. In line with this, the work of (Rodriguez-Calvo, Cossent, & Frias, 2018) proposes a methodology for scalability analysis, focusing on the functional layer, to analyse the impact of implementing smart grid functionalities in the domain of the distribution system. The methodology for the technical analysis is based mostly on the use of simulation models, representative networks and scenarios of operation in order to compute the KPIs and metrics that measure the impact of the enabled functionalities on the distribution system. For the selection of appropriate KPIs, the work in (Dupont, Meeus, & Belmans, 2010), (Efthymiou et al., 2022) may be utilised for a list of suggested KPIs for the assessment of the impact of a smart grid solution.

2.3 Technology Scaling: Scaling-up and Scaling-out Strategies

In contrast to the more business-oriented concepts of scalability and replicability discussed above, this section differentiates two technical strategies associated with technology scaling. Scaling of technology refers to the development to serve larger quantities. In information technology, *scaling up* and *scaling out* are two strategies that both aim to increase the processing power and storage capacity of systems². In this work this notion from ICT is revisited and applied to energy systems as well, considering a performance increase in the energy system in terms of energy transfer, generation or storage capacity.

Scaling up refers to increasing the capacity of a system by adding more resources to the existing infrastructure. This can involve upgrading hardware components, such as adding more memory or processing power to a server or increasing the storage capacity of a database. Scaling up is often seen as a way to improve performance and handle more complex workloads without changing the architecture of the system. In energy systems, this would correspond to increasing the component nominal power, e.g., increasing the size of a power plant or an interconnector.

On the other hand, *scaling out* involves adding more nodes to a system in order to distribute the workload and increase the overall capacity. In ICT, this can involve adding more servers to a cluster or deploying more instances of an application across multiple servers. In energy systems, this could be to increase production by deploying multiple generation units of the same type, as is common practice with wind and photovoltaic generation. For network capacity expansion this strategy would be, e.g., to divide the load on multiple parallel feeders.

In summary, both approaches scale up the demand-serving capacity of an engineered system with different advantages. *Scaling out* can also be a way to improve reliability by reducing the impact of individual component failures, and *scaling up* is focused on improving the performance of an individual system, while *scaling out* is focused on improving the overall capacity and reliability of a distributed system.

2.3.1 Domain Extension, Scale-up, and Scale-out in Power Systems

The energy system transition to a renewables-driven supply and demand-side flexibility requires a different approach to the design and validation of scaling. This section summarises

²<https://www.techopedia.com/7/31151/technology-trends/what-is-the-difference-between-scale-out-versus-scale-up-architecture-applications-etc>

the viewpoint of interpreting the energy system transition as a scaling and domain extension problem.

Scale-up vs. Scale-out

In the context of power systems, scale-up and scale-out can be used to refer to different approaches to increasing power generation capacity or network capacity. Scale-up in power systems refers to increasing the capacity of a single power generation unit or network component. This could involve increasing the size of a power plant or adding more capacity to an existing network component, such as a transformer or transmission line. Scale-up is typically achieved by increasing the physical size or rating of the component. Scale-out, on the other hand, involves adding more power generation units or network components to increase overall capacity. This could involve building new power plants or adding more renewable energy sources to an existing network. Scale-out is typically achieved by increasing the number of components or units rather than their physical size or rating. Both scale-up and scale-out approaches have their own advantages and disadvantages. In power systems, scale-up is classically viewed to be more cost-effective, since it helps to concentrate physical, management and logistics resources. However, it may also be limited by physical and environmental constraints, e.g. the available resources. Scale-out through distributed generation builds on the economy of mass production and enables flexible adapt localisation of conversion units to renewable resources and grid infrastructure. The increased flexibility on the siting and deployment, however, may require more investment in new infrastructure and may be more complex to manage.

On the example of wind power, it is clear to see that both, scale-up and scale-out strategies are combined, with ever-increasing rotor diameters of wind turbines, and large offshore wind farms being composed of multiple generation plants.

In terms of testing and validation, conventional methods in power systems are based on the assumption of a scale-up-based capacity scaling: pre-qualification, conformance, monitoring, etc., are typically oriented toward the behaviour of single or few bulk generation plants, and are specified for a single connection point. There are also practical limits to testing fully distributed plants, and it is a complex problem to state connection requirements for, e.g., virtual power plants, which would apply to a large number of distributed connection points.

Domain Extension

With domain extension, we refer to extending the scope of relevant domains considered in applications, and the analysis and assessment of energy system technologies. There are two distinct vectors of domain extension: one relates to the reliance on ICT, the other to the sourcing of flexibility.

With smart distributed infrastructure operation and remotely monitored distributed generation, the reliance on ICT becomes a potentially critical factor in the reliability and resiliency of the power system. Increasing reliance on ICT entails additional vulnerabilities, both to technical failures of the ICT infrastructure, as well as to cyber-attacks. Properly accounting for this dependency should be an element in the assessment and validation of ICT-dependent solutions.

Since flexibility on the generation side is insufficient to balance a renewables-driven power system, flexibility also needs to be made available from other points in the energy system. Here it has shown that the economics of making flexibility from the demand side are favourable. For example, since heat is easier and more cost-effective to be stored than electricity, bulk

heat generation facilities can be easily equipped with heat storage facilities, thus enabling to offset demand-serving from power conversion. However, the controllability and connection requirements on the demand side are not the same as with the generation side. Further such coupling of energy sectors may lead to additional inter-dependencies and vulnerabilities that should be accounted for. From the perspective of bulk hydrogen production, the area of energy domain extension will become even more critical.

To establish that power system testing and validation should be viewed in terms of these concerns of the domain extension, the term Cyber-Physical Energy System (CPES) was coined.

2.4 Scaling Tests and Testbed Scaling

The focus of this work is on methods and tools for the technical assessment and testing of CPES solutions. The objective of this section is to clarify how scaling and domain extension relate to testing and validation in simulation-based and laboratory environments.

2.4.1 The Role of Testbeds in Scaling Assessments

Modernisation of electricity networks necessitates testbeds for testing and validation of innovative ideas. Given the fact that a testbed is a high investment cost, the challenge arises of how to test large-scale components. Scalability is essential for reproducing simulations and tests to capture all dynamic aspects. For the testbed, it is essential to investigate how the assessment of a large-scale tested technology can be performed considering the cost-effectiveness of the experimentation.

Physical Parameter Scaling

One established approach, suitable for scale-up assessment in existing small-scale testing infrastructure, is to use an equivalent scaled-down representation of the large-scale technology. Students, researchers, and practitioners could benefit from the down-scaled laboratory representation to predict behaviours of the full system and further experiment with a number of scenarios such as changes in setting point or weather conditions. Such scaling approaches can offer a big advantage for testing and validation to reduce investment, operation and maintenance costs of testbeds (Varais, Roboam, Lacrosonnière, Bru, & Roux, 2021; Varais et al., 2018).

Testbeds for Scale-out Assessments

In the context of technology scale-out, the effects of foreseeable mass deployment in the field need to be anticipated for potential side effects or harmful interactions mitigated. Classically, this perspective was not addressed by test facilities since massive replication was only possible in field deployment. However, since more active devices are present in distribution networks, their control-based behaviour affects the bulk system dynamics and local grid stability. A research challenge is how to present an appropriate (simulated or laboratory) environment for these scaled-out technologies so that the testbed setting enables experiments that predict behaviour that would occur in the field with scaled-out technology – addressing both scaling and replication questions.

The Role of Co-simulation and Geographically distributed testbed

Two technologies that support scale-out and multi-domain assessments are co-simulation (Section 2.4.3, (*D-JRA2.1 Coupling Methods*, 2023)) and the real-time coupling of geographically distributed testbeds (Syed et al., 2021; *D-JRA2.1 Coupling Methods*, 2023). Co-simulation, including real-time co-simulation, is a technique that enables the coupling of several domain-specific simulators (e.g. power, thermal and communication networks) and supports also scale-out control systems testing via Controller Hardware-in-the-Loop (CHIL) techniques.

Geographically distributed testbeds also facilitate scale-out but are even more important for scale-up and technology maturing efforts. Especially large hardware that cannot be moved, can be integrated and facilitates coupling high-fidelity proprietary models that cannot be shared, as well as scaling up of models by coupling simulator resources.

Standard Reference Models to Enhance Reproducibility

A reference model is commonly used for testing but required configuration to represent the real system. In some cases, a real model is available for scaling up the system easily without extensive assumption parameters. For example, a typical Low Voltage (LV) grid can be represented by a reference LV grid and the loading patterns altered toward high PV and Electric Vehicle (EV) penetration.

A scaled-out simulated reference model, i.e., a composition of several copies of one or several standard reference models with distinct loading patterns, could be used to extend the capability of an existing physical tested infrastructure albeit with a limited investment budget. In this case, network operators and researchers could use a scaled model (e.g., a LV laboratory, or a representative co-simulation setup) with high DERs penetration to experiment with OLTC and ancillary services from DERs. In this way, grid stability and power quality challenges, with, e.g., demand response solutions, can be assessed in a safe environment prior to field deployment.

2.4.2 Relation Between Testbeds and Maturity Levels

The development of smart grid solutions involves various stages of testing before they become market-ready products. Testing is first implemented in a laboratory environment and probably through Hardware-in-the-Loop (HIL) and then in demonstration plants. Experience in conducting analysis of scalability, and approaches for its assessment, comes mostly from several demonstration plants in Europe (BRIDGE Horizon 2020 Task Force Replicability and Scalability Analysis, 2019),(Efthymiou et al., 2022),(Sigrist et al., 2016),(Rodriguez-Calvo et al., 2018).

The European Union has adopted the concept of Technology Readiness Level (TRL) developed by NASA involving nine levels of development stages as shown in Table 2 (Earto, 2014; Commission et al., 2017). After basic research observed TRL1 and concept formulated with prototype identification TRL2, the first laboratory or testbed will be realized which is considered in TRL3. It should be noted that in this stage, the testing only focuses on the element but not the whole system. Then, the prototype can be validated which scalable and repeatable capability in TRL4 or TRL5 depending on the technology. When the prototype can be demonstrated in a relevant environment, it is considered at TRL6 in which interoperability is presented in the pilot project. Full-scale demonstration of the prototype in an operational environment exists in TRL7. The technology is considered in TRL8 when compliance and standards can be presented with

training and maintenance documentation. Finally, an actual system fully operates commercially in TRL9.

Table 2: TRL scale used in Horizon 2020 (Earto, 2014).

TRL Scale	Description
TRL 1	Basic principles observed
TRL 2	Technology concept formulated
TRL 3	Experimental proof of concept
TRL 4	Technological validity in a lab
TRL 5	Technology validated in relevant environment
TRL 6	Technology demonstrated in relevant environment
TRL 7	System prototype demonstration in an operational environment.
TRL 8	System completed and qualified
TRL 9	Actual system proven in operational environment

Scalability and repeatability are essential for the testbed performance which should be considered in the conceptual design phase in TRL1 and TRL2 to accommodate new devices and networks in the future. Typically, a testbed could start with simple and inexpensive devices or tools in TRL3 that are set up easily and user-friendly, i.e., a small single-board computer Raspberry Pi. However, this has limitations for sophisticated tests that require powerful computation capability. Later on, a simple testbed could be scaled up to a large-scale testbed for multi-domains with many components that can be identified in TRL4 or 5. For example, the Raspberry Pi device is replaced with real industrial controllers or industrial-grade hardware connected to the testbed rack. Integrating real-time testing with standardised protocols in the laboratory is performed in TRL6 before the (full-scale) demonstration in a field test in TRL7. Testbed should be able to define in which TRL level that it can provide with its capabilities.

A testbed should provide the capability to meet research and industry needs and be also applicable for accommodating state-of-the-art technologies deployment in the future. Therefore, designing a testbed architecture should be scalable and flexible to deal with new challenges. Scaling the testbeds does not only increase the number of hardware and software components integrated (i.e. scale up) but also enhances the testbed capability (i.e. scale out) such as higher power levels (voltage and current), e.g., to mimic the substation environment (Al-Mutawaly & Al-imardani, 2013) or by integrating components in prototype, pilot or demonstrator scale. During the design phase of the testbed, an architecture of hardware and software connection should be well defined for effective operation and maintenance as well as integration of new devices in the future.

Virtualization technology can greatly support the scalability of systems as well as the CPES testbed (Green et al., 2017; Hibler et al., 2008; Huang, Chen, Shih, & Lai, 2012). With container-based virtualization technology, it could help practitioners and researchers to scale up the testing environment and capability easily. For example, replicating and/or updating new configurations of the devices can be done remotely (Krueger, Kamsamrong, & Lehnhoff, 2023). Up to date, industrial hardware provided by several vendors in power systems is capable of container-based virtualization technology.

2.4.3 Co-simulation and Simulation-based Assessment

In addition to laboratory experiments, simulation and co-simulation are very important approaches for testing. The main advantages of simulation-based testing in general are the inexpensive repeatability of experiments and the usual scaling of a experiment can be done with less effort than in a laboratory experiment. Thus, simulation-based testing is often used for first tests before implementation in laboratory or field tests.

Simulation can support scale-up analysis when a parameterisable simulation model of the relevant components is available, as the simulation can be repeated with different parameter configurations for the model to analyse the impact of these changes. But also scale-out can be implemented usually quite easily in a simulation environment as models can be instantiated multiple times to analyse the scale-out effect. Also, domain extension is often tested based on simulation. For testing in the context of the electricity grid important other domains are the sector coupling with the thermal domain or ICT for communication simulation. Co-simulation approaches aim to make these multi-domain simulations achievable. They allow the coupling of simulation components, which can be written in different programming languages, follow different modelling paradigms and represent different domains. Thus, established tools and models from domains can be reused and coupled for integrated simulation.

An overview of co-simulation frameworks can be found in (Mihal, Schvarcbacher, Rossi, & Pitner, 2022). All of these have different foci and might be more or less suitable for specific use cases. For example, the High Level Architecture (HLA) and the frameworks which base on it, allow a very detailed description of simulation components and scenarios, but this level of detail leads also to higher efforts needed to set up a simulation (Steinbrink et al., 2017). Frameworks like HELICS³ or mosaik⁴ focus more on the usability (Palmintier et al., 2017; Steinbrink et al., 2019). For example, the scenario definition in mosaik is Python-based, which allows flexible definition of simulation scenario scripts. For the coupling of simulation components, a set of methods are provided by the mosaik Application Programming Interface (API), which is also available for other programming languages than Python. In the context of this document, one use case was implemented based on mosaik (see Section 5).

Many co-simulation frameworks also support the integration of hardware devices into the simulation (HIL). That way, devices can be virtually tested in different simulated grid situations with low effort. As the partially simulated test setup might not have the same accuracy, this can not completely replace laboratory or field tests but can be a good preparation for them.

³<https://helics.org/>

⁴<https://mosaik.offis.de/>

2.4.4 Managing Complexity and Reproducibility of Scaled Experiments

Scaling out and domain extension of testbeds significantly increases the complexity, both in terms of the number of parameters and potential configurations and engineering competencies to be accommodated. This complexity poses challenges to the coordination, management and reproducibility of experiment preparation, execution and reproducible documentation.

Methods to support the experiment preparation were developed in ERIGrid and are an important aspect of ERIGrid 2.0 as well. The Holistic Test Descriptions (HTDs) methodology and framework offer templates and guidelines to aid the preparation and design of multi-domain experiments (Heussen et al., 2019). An established analytical methodology, called Design of Experiments (DoE), has been shown to be easily integrated with the HTD approach (van der Meer et al., 2018).

In order to support the analysis and assessment of large-scale phenomena and scaled-out technologies in smart grids, ERIGrid developed methods and tools (*D-JRA2.2: Smart Grid ICT assessment method*, 2018), as well as concepts (*D-JRA2.3: Smart Grid simulation environment*, 2018) to develop an appropriate assessment strategy.

In order to manage the complexity, especially of scale-out and domain-extended testing, certain lab automation can become an important enabler. ERIGrid 2.0 has focussed efforts on coupling multiple Research Infrastructures (RIs), enabling multi-RI configurations for experiments (*D-JRA2.1 Coupling Methods*, 2023; *D-JRA2.2 Software Release*, 2023). A practical usage of such multi-RI setups requires an associated automation layer handling the data flows and configuration of the participating RIs and of the joint experiment (*D-JRA2.3 Methods for Configuration Management*, 2023).

Finally, the recording and documentation of experiments and test results should aim to follow high standards of reproducibility. While at this time, there are no complete standards to support the definition of comprehensive meta-data for complex test cases, efforts should be made to document test purpose, test system configuration, as well as input and output data sets for all relevant domains of the experiment. The gold standard for documentation would be the application of the FAIR data⁵ principles throughout the experimentation phase. In complex scale-out or multi-domain test scenarios, such documentation is only practical if systematic data handling, configuration management and logging are implemented as part of the testing description and automation.

⁵FAIR Data principles, <https://force11.org/info/the-fair-data-principles/>

3 Approach

3.1 Overview

The previous section gives an overview of the terminology of scaling up, scaling out, and domain expansion. To apply this concept to the experiment, two scaling analysis approaches are presented in this section which are Type 1 (technology solution scaling) and Type 2 (impact scaling). While Type 1 focuses on the performance assessment dealing with the inherent limitation of the technology implication and how to cope with the challenges e.g., time delay in communication and interaction between elements, Type 2 aims to assess the effects of the scaling which could inform relevant stakeholders to accommodate feedback for field deployment and roll-out.

In Table 3 an overview of the approaches introduced in this section is given. It contains information about the scaling type (see Section 2.3), assessment scope (see Section 2.2), involved domains, testbed type (see Section 2.4) and references to the sections or literature describing the relevant methods, and use cases.

Table 3: Overview of approaches and case studies.

Scaling Type	Ass. Scope	Domains	Testbed Types	Methods (Sec.)	Case Study (Sec.)
Scale-up	Type 1	Power	HW, Sim, PHIL	3.2.1, 3.3.1	4.1
Scale-up	Type 2	Power	PHIL, Co-simulation	3.2.1	4.2, 5.2
Scale-out	Type 1	ICT or Power	CHIL or PHIL	3.2.2	4.3
Scale-out	Type 2	Power	CHIL or PHIL	3.2.2, 3.3.2	4.4
Domain Extension	Type 2	Power&Heat, or Power&ICT	Co-simulation, HW	3.3.4, 3.3.5	5.1

3.1.1 Test Case Analysis for Upscaling Issues

For handling upscaling issues, the analysis of the test case is the first step to make clear what kind of issue has to be handled and which approaches and methods are best suited for it. For this analysis, three layers are proposed and introduced in the following.

Layer 1: Analysis of Uncertainty and Scaling Components

The analysis of uncertainty components should be done based on a HTD description of the Test Case (TC). For that an extension of the HTD was developed in collaboration with Joint Research Activity (JRA)1.2 as described in (*D-JRA1.2 Methods for Holistic Test Reproducibility*, 2023). Experimental uncertainty components are identified in the System Configuration (SC) in order to classify the required data sources and associated uncertainty representations.

Uncertainty types are classified by uncertainty source and its relation to the experimental SC and setup. Fundamentally, as shown in Figure 1, we distinguish (i) quantifiable variability of inputs (e.g., coloured [reducible, epistemic] and white noise [irreducible, aleatory uncertainty]); (ii) identifiable uncertainties in the system structure (i.e., parametric [epistemic], structural uncertainties [model structure]) due to SC and experimental setup; and (iii) output uncertainties

due measurement and observation method (and quantification approach – e.g., human factor, discretisation).

Figure 1: Categorisation of uncertainties by system structure.

Layer 2: Defining the Experimental Purpose

The experimental purpose drives the need for quantification and decides what drives the ‘value’ of an experiment. The HTD approach has previously identified characterisation, verification and validation as generic Purpose of Investigations (PoIs). The PoI establishes the relation between targets and factors, as well as the quantification need. Each of the PoI types requires a different interpretation of the role of uncertainty in the further quantification effort, as shown in Figure 2.

Layer 3: Selection of Quantification Method and Procedure

The goal of the third layer is to minimize the costs by reducing the needed experiment runs. Thus, it is crucial to select the best suitable method for quantification and experiment design to maximise the ‘value’ of the experiment outcomes as outlined in Listing 1 and Figure 3.

The separation between aleatory and epistemic uncertainties, which was part of the first layer, helps here with the reduction of the number of experiments.

Figure 2: Categorisation by experimental purpose.

Listing 1: Quantification method example.

- (a) Apply ‘‘Monte-carlo sampling’’ to *remaining/ aleatory analysis*
- (b) Design of Experiments (DoE)
- (c) Meta-modelling (MM)
- (d) Uncertainty Quantification / Sensitivity Analysis (UQ/SA)
 - (i) screening,
 - (ii) ranking,
 - (iii) mapping,
 - (iv) identification of interactions between input factors
 - (v) MM/Response surface

3.1.2 Test Planning for Upscaling and Domain Extension

A system is considered as a collection of interconnected components with comparable boundary conditions. It is important to note that the ability of a system to scale does not necessarily guarantee that the scaled-up version of the system will perform well. Therefore, a more restrictive definition of scalability is the system’s ability to uphold its performance and functionality while maintaining all desired properties when its scale is increased without a corresponding increase in complexity (Sigrist et al., 2016; Bonnefoy & Hansman, 2008).

To formulate *Type 1* performance assessment, the system boundary is at the technology interface - e.g. the electrical terminals of a transformer, and the associated KPI.

In *Type 2* assessments, the system boundary and scope are associated with the relevant technology impacts to be investigated.

Quantitative measures are used to assess the efficiency, effectiveness, and overall performance of a system. These metrics are used to evaluate various aspects of a system, such as its speed, reliability, availability, scalability (*performance degradation of technology when ‘scaled out’*), and security.

Figure 3: Categorisation by quantification method.

3.2 Scaling-up, Scaling-out and Domain Extension Approaches

3.2.1 Scaling up

For the scale-up approach of implementing a smart grid technical solution at a larger scale, it is reasonable that physical limitations exist based on the current technological level.

Type 1

A monolithic solution will rarely be appropriate for implementation at a larger scale. For the analysis of scalability, it is useful to identify the size limits due to physical constraints, material properties, technology limitations, laws of physics etc., so that for larger sizes to investigate other solutions based, e.g., in modularity, distributed operation. An approach like this for a smart grid hardware component is presented in the test case of section 4.2, referring to a GFI. For this component, the physical limitations of its size have been identified, based on the design of the power unit and the limitations of its basic elements. Then, for the testing of a larger scale test case in a setup involving Power Hardware-in-the-Loop (PHIL), an appropriate adjustment in the interface between the Real-Time Digital Simulator (RTDS) and the power amplifier has been utilised. Concerning the ICT domain, as shown in the example presented with the Phasor Measurement Units (PMUs), the requirements for the management of high volumes of data will be increased. These massive data are acquired and stored in areas such as smart metering, substation Intelligent Electronic Devices (IEDs) and PMUs. The volume

of data is expected to grow by orders of magnitude both in terms of size and frequency of measurements. A scalable high-performance computational infrastructure would be required in order to handle these high volumes of data and efficiently perform the data analysis tasks required for extracting relevant information. Researchers in the field of computer science have had a long experience with these issues during the last few years and much progress has been made in developing scalable computational frameworks that address these needs.

Much work has been devoted also to studying the scalability of the technologies involved in the smart grid (type 1 perspective, technology solution scaling). In order to enable large-scale deployment, smart grid solutions must be able to cope with increasing volumes of information and interacting agents. Therefore, the scalability of solutions is analysed in terms of the capability of information technologies, algorithms, communications and systems to exchange, analyze and store large volumes of data and perform large-scale computations.

Type 2

An example from literature (NERC, 2010) may be presented, on the analysis of requirements, of ICT domain mainly, introduced by a large-scale application of a smart grid solution. The use of PMU is considered of high importance for the operation of future smart grids characterised by large penetration of variable RES, particularly for applications requiring real-time observational data on a wide area of the grid. PMUs usually sample at speeds of 30 observations per second (compared to conventional monitoring technologies, such as Supervisory Control and Data Acquisition (SCADA), that measure once every two to four seconds), with each PMU making about 20 measurements (sixteen of these are 8 phasor measurements with a magnitude and angle for each). A network of 40 PMUs supplying data to a hosting data centre would require a communications bandwidth of approx. 836 kbits/s, as calculated by taking into account the digital representation of the measured values. Similarly, the storage requirements for this case are calculated to amount to some terabytes per year.

3.2.2 Scaling out

Type 1

A typical approach for assessing the impacts of a technical solution to the grid is through simulation and calculation of specific metrics, such as KPIs. This approach is illustrated in the example of Section 4.3, where the scale-out of microgrids, in a rather research-level concept of multi-microgrid, are analysed by simulations in order to assess metrics related to power quality or power losses.

Type 2

Much work is currently being carried out to determine the potential impacts that can be expected from the implementation of smart grid solutions (type-2 perspective, impact scaling). The transfer of results from the implementation of a pilot smart grid project or a testing procedure to the large-scale implementation of the smart grid solution involves a scaling analysis. Conclusions are drawn from experimental data by extrapolating and performing Sensitivity Analysis (SA) assuming certain hypotheses.

An example of studying the effects of interactions among components, in an upscaled implementation of a technical solution, is given in Section 4.4. This test case represents a scale-out

approach and deals with the voltage control in a portion of the grid. Voltage control is accomplished mostly locally in distribution grids, by utilising various components and control techniques, such as OLTC transformers or power inverters with advanced functions. These various means of control acting at the same time for the regulation of local voltage make the effects of interactions unavoidable. The effects of a technical solution aiming to provide voltage control on the operation of all the components participating in the task of local voltage control would require normally a detailed simulation in order to be analysed. The example in Section 4.4 deals with the interaction and assessment of the parallel operation of two OLTC transformers. The analysis is made through simulation of the representative network developed in the ‘Electric Network’ benchmark.

3.2.3 Domain Extension

For a multi-factor complex process with a high dimensional input domain, SA is an important tool as it allows the identification of the more significant factors that affect the results and limit the investigation in an input domain of reduced dimensions. A variance based SA (e.g., Sobol indices) is particularly useful for the factor prioritization setting, as it can systematically quantify and rank the importance of each factor, taking into account possible interactions.

An example of using this approach is presented in the case of the Multi-Energy (ME) benchmark, in Section 5. This particular example emphasises also the use of a co-simulation framework for performing a multi-domain analysis. The smart grid is a heterogeneous CPES composed of different physical and computational components interacting through communications networks. They represent different simulation domains that are modelled by means of domain-specific modelling languages with unique semantics and simulation tools. The use of a single ‘universal’ modelling language to fit the needs of all smart grid domains seems to be impractical, with the solution being a co-simulation approach that facilitates the integration of heterogeneous, multi-model simulations.

3.3 Analytical Methods to Support Scaling Analysis

This section summarises the analytical methods relevant to this guideline. Similitude theory enables the consistent representation of physical phenomena occurring in a full-scale system down to a reduced “testbed” scale, thereby supporting scale-up testing efforts.

Further analytical methods consider the quantitative and qualitative sensitivity analysis in regard to upscaling and their relation with uncertainty quantification.

3.3.1 Physical Parameter Scaling

Physical parameter scaling aims to conduct experiments on a scaled model system and apply the obtained results to the full-scale system. Similitude theory, a branch of engineering science, establishes the necessary conditions for similarity among phenomena. This theory defines the behaviour of a physical system using a complete set of dimensionless variables formed by relevant physical variables. According to this theory, two systems behave similarly under the same experimental conditions if their dimensionless variables have the same values. Thus, the comparison of the two systems can be made by comparing their dimensionless quantities. Similitude theory-based size-scale models are widely used in various scientific fields. This theory has been critical in experimental mechanics, as documented in the extensive review in

(Coutinho et al., 2016). In addition, the use of this approach for the development of scaled models is also gaining popularity in the field of electrical engineering (Petersheim & Brennan, 2009). With that, by applying scaling laws to the experimental results of a scale model related to the prototype by similarity conditions, similitude theory enables engineers and scientists to accurately predict the behaviours of the prototype, as illustrated in Figure 4.

Figure 4: Outline a method for predicting the structural behaviour of an oversized prototype by using the experimental results obtained from a scaled model (Coutinho et al., 2016).

Langhaar (Langhaar, 1951) provided a mathematical definition of similarity, which can be stated as follows; the function f' is similar to the function f , provided the ratio f'/f is a constant when the functions are evaluated for homologous points and homologous times. The constant $\lambda=f'/f$ is called the scale factor for the function f . Szucs (Szucs, 1980) later proposed that if a system can be represented using a mathematical model, then the necessary and sufficient condition for similitude between two systems is that the mathematical model of one must be related to the other by a bi-unique transformation. This implies that given the characteristic vectors of the prototype X_p and model X_m , which include all the parameters and variables of the systems, a transformation matrix $[\Lambda]$ can be derived:

$$X_p = [\Lambda]X_m, \text{ or } X_m = [\Lambda]^{-1}X_p \quad (1)$$

Physical Size-Scaling of Parameters based on Similitude Theory

The laws of physics remain unchanged regardless of any change in the unit of measurement. This fundamental property enables the description of a physical system's behaviour by a comprehensive set of dimensionless variables derived from relevant physical quantities. Consequently, comparing physical systems becomes possible by comparing their dimensionless quantities. The Vaschy-Buckingham theorem (Buckingham, 1914) (also known as the π theorem), which is a fundamental theorem of dimensional analysis, establishes the maximum number of independent dimensionless numbers that can be formed in a physical problem involving n variables. Using the Buckingham theorem, a physical problem that involves n variables can be transformed into a problem of dimension $k = n - r$, where k is expressed in terms of dimensionless numbers. Here, r represents the number of independent physical dimensions.

The application of the similitude theory has several objectives (Varais et al., 2018):

- Proposing independent dimensionless numbers (called π -groups),
- Simplifying basic equations by eliminating irrelevant variables,
- Establishing criteria for a scale experiment to represent a full-scale experiment, and
- Providing scale change relationships between the reduced scale experiments and the full-scale phenomenon.

After that, a table consisting of four matrices, namely A, B, C, and D, is created (Szirtes, 2006):

- Matrices A and B consist of exponents associated with the fundamental dimensions of the parameter/variable unit.
- The choice of repeating parameters can be arbitrary, as long as matrix A is invertible, but it is recommended to select the parameters that will be scaled to simplify calculations.
- Matrix D should be in its simplest form to produce the simplest possible π -groups, and it is common to use the identity matrix to enable a decoupling between π -groups and the model's parameters/variables to be reduced. Each π -group depends on a single parameter/variable and certain repeating parameters.
- Matrix C is determined through the following calculation:

$$C = -D(A^{-1}B)^T \quad (2)$$

Using this table, it becomes possible to establish the formulas for various π -groups, which consist of a single parameter/variable in combination with repeating parameters.

To determine the scaled model parameters, the concept of "scale factor" is used. A scale factor S_x is associated with a specific physical variable x and is calculated as the ratio of the scaled variable to its original counterpart:

$$S_x = \frac{x_{scaled}}{x_{original}} \quad (3)$$

Each variable or parameter has a corresponding scale factor, which can be obtained directly from the π -group associated with it. The relationship between the scale factor and the π -group is described by a specific equation known as the "Model Law" (Varais et al., 2018).

3.3.2 Scaling out Analysis: Fractal Theory

Fractal-based modelling techniques refer to the application of fractal principles and mathematical concepts to model and analyse complex systems. These techniques aim to capture the self-similarity, iterative nature, and spatial complexity observed in fractals and apply them to model real-world phenomena. In the context of power systems and scaling out, fractal-based modelling techniques can be utilised to understand and analyse the behaviour of the system at various scales. An example of using fractal theory for real power networks planning, and scaling analysis in the French distribution system is presented in (Sidqi, 2019).

Fractal-based modelling techniques can be applied to scale out microgrids by capturing the complex and self-similar characteristics of their deployment and operation. The practical implementation of fractal-based modelling techniques in scaling out microgrids is an ongoing area of research. The specific approaches may vary depending on the microgrid system's characteristics, deployment scale, and desired objectives. Nonetheless, utilising fractal principles can facilitate the expansion, operation, and optimisation of microgrids within the larger power system, supporting the effective scaling out of decentralized power generation and enhancing system resilience. Here are some ways in which fractal-based modelling techniques can be used in scaling out microgrids:

- *Fractal-Inspired Microgrid Expansion*: By considering the self-similarity and scaling properties of fractals, models can guide the iterative expansion of microgrids. These models

take into account factors such as load density, renewable resource availability, and network connectivity to determine the optimal placement and size of new microgrids as the system grows.

- *Fractal Modelling of Load and Generation*: Fractal-based models can capture the patterns and dependencies in load and generation within microgrids. This helps improve load forecasting accuracy and optimize the sizing and operation of local generation resources, energy storage systems, and demand response mechanisms.
- *Fractal Analysis of Energy Flow*: Fractal-based modelling techniques analyze the energy flow dynamics within interconnected microgrids. By considering the self-similarity and spatial complexity of energy flows, these models optimize energy dispatch, load sharing, and power exchange between interconnected microgrids, improving overall system efficiency and resilience.
- *Fractal-Inspired Control and Optimisation*: Fractal principles guide the design of control and optimisation strategies for scaling out microgrids. By leveraging the recursive interconnection and self-similarity properties, these techniques enable coordinated operation, adaptive management, and self-healing capabilities in interconnected microgrids.

3.3.3 Design of Experiments

From the perspective of technical testing, an objective in test planning and design can be formulated in the question “Given my limited budget, how can I gain as much information as possible?” To this end, the DoE theory, introduced by (Fisher, 1936), offers sampling strategies that maximise this information. In particular, DoE is relevant, when a large number of parameters need to be tuned with a limited set of experiments. The applicability of DoE to power systems and CPES testing has been demonstrated during the ERIGrid project, and a mapping to the ERIGrid HTD method has been provided (van der Meer et al., 2018). Applications of DoE to electrical engineering and control design were discussed in (Maussion, 2017). An application of Design of Experiments for an energy system sizing problem is presented in (Zaibi et al., 2018), where DoE is used to derive a Meta-model (Section 3.3.5).

Whereas HTD aids in scoping an experiment (“What is the main purpose of running this experiment?” and “What do I hope to be able to show?”), DoE provides a formal mathematical framework, once the testing objectives, metrics and factor constraints have been clarified. In practice, a gap remains between the formulation of a basic HTD and the possibility of directly applying the analytical DoE approach. Here the extended HTD factor analysis is suggested to be applied, as presented in (*D-JRA1.2 Methods for Holistic Test Reproducibility*, 2023).

According to (Dean, Voss, & Draguljic, 2017), typically, an experiment may be run for one or more of the following reasons:

- (i) to determine the principal causes of variation in a measured response,
- (ii) to find the conditions that give rise to maximum or minimum response,
- (iii) to compare the responses achieved at different settings of controllable variables, or
- (iv) to obtain a mathematical model in order to predict future responses.

Primarily, the DoE approach offers a toolbox and a standard framework to support the sample design and result evaluation for experiments. The following sections will present analyt-

ical methods and steps to deepen the analysis with regard to the above experimental purposes.

A practical checklist, defined in (Dean et al., 2017), summarises the DoE framework and its main concepts:

- (a) Define the objectives of the experiment
- (b) Identify all sources of variation, including:
 - (i) treatment factors and their levels,
 - (ii) experimental units,
 - (iii) blocking factors, noise factors, and covariates
- (c) Choose a rule for assigning the experimental units to the treatments.
- (d) Specify the measurements to be made, the experimental procedure, and the anticipated difficulties.
- (e) Run a pilot experiment.
- (f) Specify the model.
- (g) Outline the analysis.
- (h) Calculate the number of observations that need to be taken.
 - (i) Review the above decisions. Revise, if necessary.

The concepts of *factors* and *targets* (above: objectives) are adopted in this work, attributing to the DoE approach.

3.3.4 Sensitivity Analysis (SA)

According to (Steinbrink, 2017), sensitivity analysis is a process that is related to uncertainty quantification. While quantification aims at identifying the output uncertainty of a simulation model based on initial uncertainties, the goal of sensitivity analysis is the identification of the effect of a given uncertainty source on the output uncertainty. It is an important tool for assessing the reliability and accuracy of model predictions, as well as for identifying the most important sources of uncertainty and variability in a system.

Typical questions addressed by SA are as follows (Pianosi et al., 2016):

- What input factors cause the largest variation in the output?
- Is there any factor whose variability has a negligible effect on the output?
- Is there any interaction that amplifies or dampens the variability induced by individual factors?

Sensitivity analysis can be divided into *Local Sensitivity Analysis (LSA)* and *Global Sensitivity Analysis (GSA)* under the input space point of view and into OAT and All-(factors)-At-a-Time (AAT) based on the sampling approach (Pianosi et al., 2016). The local analysis aims to evaluate the input-to-output variability close to a given system state or parameter, applying a local factor variation. However, the applicability of LSA is valid only for ‘small’ changes, and it is limited to just a narrow range around the system state unless the model is proven to be linear in all its inputs. In contrast, the global sensitivity analysis aims at exploring the whole

input space, i.e., by encompassing the full range of model inputs' variability, and not just the immediate vicinity of the system state (Ginocchi, Ponci, & Monti, 2021).

Mainly, LSA commonly uses OAT sampling, while GSA can use either OAT or AAT strategies. In OAT approaches, the model inputs are varied one by one while all others remain at baseline values. Meanwhile, AAT approaches involve a simultaneous variation of model inputs, such as through Monte Carlo simulations.

Three main purposes of the SA are identified in the literature:

1. *Screening* (or Factor Fixing) seeks to identify the input factors, if any, which have a negligible influence on the output variability.
2. *Ranking* (or Factor Prioritization) seeks to generate the ranking of the input factors x_1, x_2, \dots, x_M , according to their relative contribution to the output variability.
3. *Mapping* seeks to determine the region of the input variability space that produces significant, e.g., extreme output values.

In turn, SA can be assessed through a quantitative or a qualitative approach. The former involves quantifying the sensitivity of a model's output to changes in input parameters, often using statistical methods such as regression analysis or variance-based methods like Sobol's indices. This approach is useful for identifying the relative importance of different input parameters, assessing the robustness of model predictions, and reducing the overall dimension of the problem by identifying non-influential parameters that can be discarded.

On the other hand, the qualitative approach involves a more exploratory focus, where model responses are examined for qualitative changes as parameters are varied. This approach is useful for identifying potential non-linear behaviour and interactions between input parameters that may not be apparent through quantitative analysis alone by using tools like (Pianosi et al., 2016) tornado plots, scatter plots, parallel coordinate plots, or similar representations.

Besides, both quantitative and qualitative SA are important for upscaling, which involves either the process of increasing the size of models or the multiplicity of them. Upscaling often introduces additional uncertainties, as the behaviour of a system at larger scales may differ from that at smaller scales due to the effects of heterogeneity, scaling laws, and other factors, including (Kleijnen & Sargent, 2000; Pianosi et al., 2016; Ghanem, Higdon, & Owhadi, 2017; Ginocchi et al., 2021):

- *Model approximation*: When upscaling, small-scale models are often approximated by larger-scale models with different assumptions and simplifications. These approximations can introduce errors and uncertainties in the predictions.
- *Boundary conditions*: When upscaling, it may involve changing the boundary conditions of a system, e.g., in the power system context, it implies voltage and frequency levels, power flow limits, and system stability constraints, which can significantly affect its behaviour. Uncertainties in the boundary conditions can thus propagate to the larger-scale model predictions.
- *Parameter estimation*: Estimating parameters for large-scale models can be challenging due to the lack of available data and the complexity of the models. This can introduce uncertainties in the parameter estimates, which can then affect the predictions of the larger-scale model.
- *Calibration*: Large-scale models may require calibration to match observed data. However, the calibration process introduces uncertainties in the model predictions, as it in-

volves adjusting the model parameters to fit the data.

- *Extrapolation*: Upscaling often involves extrapolating the behaviour of a system from small to large scales, which can introduce uncertainties due to the lack of experimental data at larger scales.
- *Computational limitations*: Upscaling may require significant computational resources, which can introduce uncertainties due to numerical approximations and errors.

In this sense, by performing sensitivity analyses on both small and large-scale models, researchers can better understand the effects of upscaling on model behaviour and identify the key parameters that drive predictions at different scales.

3.3.5 Meta-Modeling

The various SA methods for evaluating multiple input factors involve a large number of model evaluations, as is shown in Figure 6, which can be a problem when substantial time (e.g., in the order of hours) is required per each evaluation. An approach of using a meta-model (or surrogate model) offers a solution to the infeasibility of applying SA in this case.

A computational model is a ‘black box’ program that can be considered as a mapping of a vector $x = \{x_1, x_2, \dots, x_N\}$ of N input parameters to an output quantity of interest y

$$y = f(x)$$

A meta-model is a mathematical function $\hat{f}(x)$ which is a statistical approximation of the original function $f(x)$. It is built from a relatively limited number of evaluations of the original computational model, which are used in order to produce a set of pairs of input-output samples. For each input sample point $x^k = \{x_1^k, \dots, x_N^k\}$ $k = 1, 2, \dots, K$ the model is evaluated, to produce a set of K values of model output y^k $k = 1, 2, \dots, K$. These training data (pairs (x^k, y^k)) are processed to build the meta-model through a learning algorithm. Following this, the approximation can be used for SA calculations, at a negligible computational cost. The gain of this approach is 2-3 orders of magnitude less evaluations, compared to a typical Monte Carlo simulation. Several types of models can be used for the building of the approximate function, such as Polynomial Chaos Expansions (PCES), kriging (also known as Gaussian process modelling), Reduced-Order Model (ROM), and Artificial Neural Network (ANN).

3.3.6 Uncertainty Analysis

Uncertainty analysis investigates the effects of lack of knowledge or potential errors on model inputs (e.g., the uncertainty associated with parameter values) (Gaber et al., 2009). In the context of modelling, there can be many sources of uncertainty. However, it is convenient to categorise the character of uncertainties as either aleatory or epistemic (Kiureghian & Ditlevsen, 2009). Aleatory uncertainty is one that is presumed to be the intrinsic randomness of a phenomenon. Epistemic uncertainty is one that is presumed to be caused by a lack of knowledge (or data). Epistemic uncertainties may introduce dependence among random events, which may not be properly noted if modelled as aleatory variables (Mulenga, Bollen, & Etherden, 2021). Different data sets are needed for each type of uncertainty. For example, to obtain realistic results from practical hosting-capacity studies, a survey may be conducted to determine the number of customers (epistemic uncertainty) willing to install PV in future. However, the actual number of customers that will install PV is not known. For aleatory uncertainties, measurements are needed.

According to (Steinbrink, 2017), uncertainty may be perceived from three different angles, as shown in Figure 5. *Uncertainty flavour* refers to the way in which analysts lack knowledge about aspects of reality, e.g., ignore information or phenomena because they are negligible. *Uncertainty manifestation* describes the characteristic of a simulation model about which uncertainty exists, like input data, model equations, model implementation, etc. *Uncertainty representation* indicates which uncertainty models may be used to describe the uncertainty about a given manifestation or source mathematically.

Figure 5: Suggested attributes for uncertainty description (A) and their connection to the standard uncertainty classification (B) (Steinbrink, 2017).

The separation between aleatory and epistemic uncertainties helps with the reduction of the number of experiments. A guideline to uncertainty analysis and quantification in testing is presented in an accompanying ERIGrid 2.0 report (*D-JRA1.2 Methods for Holistic Test Reproducibility*, 2023).

3.3.7 Sensitivity and Uncertainty Analysis

According to (Saltelli et al., 2007), a SA method should be characterised by (i) its ability to handle scale/shape effects by incorporating the entire variation range of inputs and their distribution, (ii) including multidimensional averaging to explore the input space at a global level by varying all inputs simultaneously to identify potential interactions, (iii) being a 'model-free', meaning it can be applied and trusted without relying on any preconceived notions about the model's properties or validity, (iv) its ability to handle groups of model inputs as a single entity to make interpreting results more efficient and flexible.

Selecting the most appropriate SA method for a given problem is mainly driven by the purpose of the analysis (screening, ranking or mapping) and computational burden available capacity,

as shown in Figure 6⁶. Similar methods like One-way SA, Differential SA, Scenario Analysis, and Tornado diagram for LSA, and the Morris method for GSA can be found in (Ginocchi et al., 2021).

Figure 6: Sensitivity Analysis techniques for evaluating multiple input factors based on the purposes of the analysis (Pianosi et al., 2016).

3.3.8 Uncertainty Quantification vs. Sensitivity Analysis

One of the processes with the strongest connection to Uncertainty Quantification (UQ) is SA. It aims the identification of those uncertainty sources that have the strongest effect on a system's output uncertainty. Therefore, SA and UQ are often conducted in combination – at best, in an iterative manner. A UQ setup facilitates the application of SA; i.e., if a UQ system is established, it may also be used to conduct SA. This is most commonly done by assuming some input sources to be certain. The UQ setup is then used to study the effect of the remaining sources. Figure 7 provides an overview of this approach.

⁶**EET**: Elementary Effect Test, **DELSA**: Distributed Evaluation of Local Sensitivity Analysis, **CC**: Pearson Correlation Coefficient, **PCC**: Partial Correlation Coefficient, **SRCC**: Spearman Rank Correlation Coefficient, **PRCC**: Partial Rank Correlation Coefficient, **CCA**: Canonical Correlation Analysis, **SRC**: Standardised Regression Coefficients, **CART**: Classification and Regression Trees, **FAST**: Fourier Amplitude Sensitivity Test, **eFAST**: extended-FAST, **VBSA**: Variance-based SA.

Figure 7: Framework and main process of UQ (Zhang et al., 2020).

On the other hand, SA results may be used to increase UQ performance by disregarding uncertainty sources that have little effect on the output uncertainty. Nevertheless, SA is also a self-contained research field with various methods aside from the simple ‘fixing’ of uncertainty sources. For example, consider the model in Figure 8 described by the function $y = f(x_1, x_2)$. In this case, uncertainty analysis is conducted by finding how y responds to variation in inputs x_1 and x_2 , which is referred to as the model’s response surface. Sensitivity analysis is performed by apportioning the respective contributions of x_1 and x_2 to changes in y . Therefore, when UQ and SA are conducted in combination, these allow model users to be more informed about the confidence that can be placed in model results.

Figure 8: Representation of uncertainty analysis and sensitivity analysis (Gaber et al., 2009).

4 Case Studies for Power System Scaling Up and Out

Nowadays, the electric power system has become more complex to analyse and operate due to the spreading of converter-based technologies, such as renewable resources, energy storage systems, and non-linear loads. This trend has pushed up power system engineers and researchers to derive network benchmark models of the electrical system, either for planning or operation, as reference cases to assess its behaviour in different scales.

Therefore, when it is foreseen to evaluate the behaviour of the power system on a larger scale, either from scaling up or out of the perspective of the technologies or the network, these types of reference models become helpful. By studying these types of cases, researchers can identify the best practices and strategies for scaling up and out the power system or the technologies on it. In this sense, this section explores four power system case studies related to scalability in terms of scale-up and scale-out, examining the challenges faced, the solutions developed, and the outcomes achieved. These examples highlight the importance of dealing with scaling up and out in power system analysis, providing valuable insights into the future of energy generation and distribution.

4.1 Scaling up OLTC Transformer in a Low Voltage Network

In order to assess the effect of scaling up the network's assets, the distribution LV network from (*D-JRA1.1 Benchmark Scenarios, 2022*) was selected. It was designed to serve as a standard setup for carrying out electrical system simulations in the phasor domain using Simulink/MATLAB environment. The primary objective of this reference setup is to establish a standard for quasi-dynamic simulations of LV distribution systems, including loads and DERs (PV and energy storage), over extended periods, such as hours or days. The models of the components, along with the level of detail, were defined to facilitate simulations and evaluate different features, such as voltage control coordination, power distribution among DERs, and especially the OLTCs functionality of the grid transformer. The single-line diagram and the detail of the distribution system case study are presented in Figure 9 and Tables 4 and 5, respectively.

Figure 9: Simulink diagram of the “Electric Network” benchmark model (phasor version) (*D-JRA1.1 Benchmark Scenarios, 2022*).

Table 4: Grid benchmark parameters.

Description	Symbol	Value	Unit
Power source			
Phase-Vo-phase voltage	V_{rms}	20	kV
Phase angle of phase A	θ_A	0	deg
Nominal frequency	f_n	50	Hz
Source resistance	R_s	0.614577	Ohms
Source inductance	H_s	0.00163022	H
Base voltage	V_{rms}^{ph-ph}	20	kV
Residential Load			
Nominal power*	P_L	230	kW
Power factor	PF	0.95	p.u.
Timestep	Δt	15	minutes
Constant Load			
Active power*	P_c	10	kW
Nominal phase-to-phase voltage	V_{rms}^n	0.4	kV
Inductive reactive power*	Q_L	1	kvar
Capacitive reactive power	Q_C	0	kvar
Photovoltaic system*			
Peak power	P_{pv}	10	kWp
BESS system			
Rated power*	P_{BESS}^r	15	kW
Rated capacity*	C_{BESS}	75	kWh
Initial stored energy	SOC_{ini}	50	%
System efficiency	eff_{BESS}	96	%
Maximum power allowed from the grid *	P_{max}^{ex}	27.5	kW
Maximum charging power*	$P_{BESS,max}^{charge}$	27.5	kW
Regulator integral gain*		100	Unit
Distribution lines*			
Line 1 resistance	R_{line1}	1.491	Ohms
Line 1 reactance	X_{line1}	0.00082	Ohms
Line 2 resistance	R_{line2}	0.2485	Ohms
Line 2 reactance	X_{line2}	0.00014	Ohms
Line 3 resistance	R_{line3}	0.994	Ohms
Line 3 reactance	X_{line3}	0.00055	Ohms
Line 4 resistance	R_{line4}	1.491	Ohms
Line 4 reactance	X_{line4}	0.00082	Ohms
Line 5 resistance	R_{line5}	0.497	Ohms
Line 5 reactance	X_{line5}	0.00027	Ohms
Line 6 resistance	R_{line6}	0.497	Ohms
Line 6 reactance	X_{line6}	0.00027	Ohms

* Scaled parameters

Table 5: Transformer parameters.

Description	Symbol	Value	Unit
Transformer parameters			
Nominal power*	P_n^T	250	kVA
Nominal frequency	f_n	50	Hz
Winding 1 parameters: V1 Ph-Ph	V_{rms}^1	20	kV
Winding 1 parameters: Resistance	R_1	0.003	p.u.
Winding 1 parameters: Reactance	X_1	0.09	p.u.
Winding 2 parameters: V2 Ph-Ph	V_{rms}^2	0.4	kV
Winding 2 parameters: Resistance	R_2	0.003	p.u.
Winding 2 parameters: Reactance	X_2	0.09	p.u.
Initial pos. seq. output currents of winding 2	Mag	0.15	p.u.
Initial pos. seq. output currents of winding 2	$Phase$	50	deg
Magnetization branch: Resistance	R_m	300	p.u.
Magnetization branch: Reactance	X_m	300	p.u.

* Scaled parameters

Following the principle of the similitude theory described in (Varais et al., 2018), the aim of this case was to scale all the assets in the distribution network with respect to the OLTC dynamic position with a scale factor $S_x = 3$. This means that the rated power of the distribution transformer is scaled to 750 kVA.

Figure 10 compares the tap changer operation for both the original and scaled-up cases. It can be seen that the operation of both OLTC controllers depicts similar results when the system is scaled-up. The mismatch between both curves is due to the quasi-dynamic simulation runs with a different time resolution.

Figure 10: Comparison of the OLTC behaviour by scaling up the distribution MV/LV transformer.

This example highlights the importance of identifying relevant factors that will affect the results, in this case, of the scaled system. This means that not only the technology (OLTC transformer)

needs to be scaled up but also the assets of the distribution network to reproduce the behaviour of the reference case.

4.2 Scaling up of a Grid-Forming Inverter

This section presents the detailed GFI scaling-up procedures and their associated dynamic stability analysis, which are elaborated on from the perspective of a holistic simulation system and the real-time PHIL setup incorporating a physical GFI. These provide a guideline for scaling up the individual GFI power capability and offer insights into its inherent impact on scaled-up system operation.

Section A: GFI Power Scaling-up in Holistic Simulation System

This subsection presents the detailed procedures for scaling up the power of GFI with emphasis placed on the generic modelling of GFI along with its control system, the scale-up taxonomy of GFI and its associated components and control parameters variations, and the resultant dynamic stability analysis according to the power scale-up levels. Here we provide some criteria for the proper scaling up of GFI for pure simulation applications.

1. Generic Modelling of GFI and Nested Control

A representation of a two-level three-phase GFI system diagram is illustrated in Figure 11, where inner current and voltage control loops are employed. These nested control loops, as presented in Figure 12 are modelled as follows:

Figure 11: A representation of a two-level three-phase GFI system diagram with inner current and outer voltage control loops.

Figure 12: A representation of inner current and outer voltage control loops.

Inner Current Control Loop

The objective of this control loop is to control the converter output current (i) by regulating the converter output voltage (v_{inv}), i.e., generating a proper converter output voltage reference.

According to the circuit diagram presented in Figure 11, based on Kirchhoff's law, the output currents and output voltages of GFI can be expressed as:

$$\begin{cases} L \frac{di_a}{dt} + Ri_a = v_{inva} - v_{oa}, \\ L \frac{di_b}{dt} + Ri_b = v_{invb} - v_{ob}, \\ L \frac{di_c}{dt} + Ri_c = v_{invc} - v_{oc}, \end{cases} \quad (4)$$

where L and R represent the inductance of the output filter and its parasitic resistance, respectively. v_{inv} and v_o represent the GFI output voltage and the voltage at the PCC between the GFI output filter and load or grid, respectively.

Applying abc to $dq0$ transformation (Park Transform), Eq. (4) is further expressed as

$$\begin{cases} L \frac{di_d}{dt} + Ri_d - \omega Li_q = v_{invd} - v_{od}, \\ L \frac{di_q}{dt} + Ri_q + \omega Li_d = v_{invq} - v_{oq}. \end{cases} \quad (5)$$

From a control point of view, the interactive d and q currents lead to a complicated control structure, and the PCC voltage v_o (i.e., voltage disturbance) distorts the control dynamics. To mitigate these impacts, the converter output voltage references (v_{dinv}^* and v_{qinv}^*) can be modified by implementing additive decoupling term and feed-forward term, which yields

$$\begin{cases} L \frac{di_d}{dt} + Ri_d = v_{dinv}^* = v_{invd} - v_{od} + \omega Li_q, \\ L \frac{di_q}{dt} + Ri_q = v_{qinv}^* = v_{invq} - v_{oq} - \omega Li_d. \end{cases} \quad (6)$$

By doing so, as shown in Eq. (6), the d-axis and q-axis grid side current are decoupled, and the corresponding equivalent frequency-domain block diagram of the GFI in the dq-frame is illustrated in Figure 13.

Figure 13: A representation of a two-level three-phase GFI system diagram with inner current and outer voltage control loops.

Outer voltage control loop

In analogy to the modelling of the inner current control loop, the decoupling mechanism can be applied to the outer voltage control loop (or PQ control loop) to derive its modelling in the dq-frame and its corresponding equivalent frequency-domain block diagram.

2. GFI Power Scaling-up

In terms of scaling up a GFI with a higher power rating, the extent to which the GFI power can be scaled up is mainly determined by its rated output current and output voltage. While the former is mainly constrained by the threshold that is designed for the protection purpose of the

switches utilized in GFI, and the latter depends on the available DC voltage source and its rated level. The relationship between the DC voltage level to be scaled and the rated output voltage is tabulated in Table 6. Subsequently, depending on desired power rating (to be scaled), the rated current can be calculated as presented in Table 6. Based on the nominal power, voltage, and current, the nominal impedance of the candidate GFI can be calculated accordingly, and the detailed mathematical calculations are listed in Table 6.

Table 6: GFC rated variables (power, voltage, frequency, impedance).

Description	Symbol	Unit	Value
DC voltage	V_{DC}	V	To be scaled
Nominal Power	S_{nom}	kW	To be scaled
Nominal Voltage	V_{nom}	V	$\frac{V_{DC}}{1.15 \times \sqrt{2}}$
Nominal Current	I_{nom}	A	$\frac{S_{nom}}{\sqrt{3}V_{nom}}$
Nominal Frequency	f_{nom}	Hz	50
Nominal Impedance	Z_{nom}	Ω	$\frac{V_{nom}}{\sqrt{3}I_{nom}}$
Nominal Inductance	L_{nom}	H	$Z_{nom} \frac{1}{2\pi f_{nom}}$
Nominal Capacitance	C_{nom}	F	$\frac{1}{2\pi f_{nom} Z_{nom}}$

Table 7: GFC control and component parameters.

Description	Symbol	Unit	Value
Sampling and switching frequency			
Switching Frequency	f_{sw}	kHz	20
Sampling Frequency (single update)	f_s	kHz	f_{sw}
Sampling Frequency (double update)	f_s	kHz	$2f_{sw}$
Sampling Time	T_s	s	$1/f_s$
GFC output filters			
Filter Capacitance	C_f	F	$0.05 C_{nom}$
Filter Inductance	L_f	H	$\frac{1}{(2\pi f_{sw}/10)^2 C_f}$
Inductance Parasitic Resistance	R_f	Ω	$\frac{0.05 Z_{nom}}{100}$

Once the rated impedance is obtained by following the criteria listed in Table 6, the next step is to design the output filters. Apart from the rated value as presented in Table 6, the switching frequency is another important aspect that determines the switching loss, efficiency, etc. For simulation purposes, as presented in Table 7, the sampling time is selected according to the Pulse width Modulation (PWM) update mode (i.e., single or double update mode). Based on the nominal impedance and switching frequency, the optimal output filter impedance value can be calculated for attenuating switching frequency components with optimal efficiency. The control parameters for the GFI nested controller can be subsequently designed according to the sampling time and output filter parameters.

3. Dynamic Stability Analysis

As presented in Section A.2, to realise a power scale-up of a GFI, the system output filters and control parameters need to be adjusted according to the criteria listed in Table 6 and Table 7.

Figure 14: Block diagram of inner current and outer voltage control loops in dq-frame.

To support the stability analysis of the GFI system with power scale, according to the system modelling in Section A.1, the dq-frame power converter control system that is illustrated in Figure 12 is expressed in the form of a single-input-single-output system and the resultant frequency-domain block diagram is shown in Figure 14.

The inner current loop, as encircled by the green dashed line in Figure 14, comprises the current PI controller, the equivalent time delay stemming from the computation (one time step T_s) and PWM generation (half time step $0.5T_s$), and the output filters. The open-loop transfer function of the current control loop is given by,

$$G_{iop}(s) = \frac{(k_{pc} + k_{ic}/s)e^{-1.5sT_s}}{Ls + R}, \quad (7)$$

where k_{pc} and k_{ic} are the proportional gain and integral gain of the current PI controller.

Furthermore, the closed-loop transfer function of the current control loop is given by,

$$G_{icl}(s) = \frac{(k_{pc}s + k_{ic})e^{-1.5sT_s}}{Ls^2 + Rs + (k_{pc}s + k_{ic})e^{-1.5sT_s}}. \quad (8)$$

The open-loop transfer function of the outer voltage control loop is expressed as,

$$G_{vop}(s) = \frac{(k_{pv} + k_{iv}/s)G_{icl}(s)}{Cs}, \quad (9)$$

where k_{pv} and k_{iv} are the proportional gain and integral gain of the voltage PI controller.

Substituting Eq. (8) into Eq. (9), the open-loop transfer function of the outer voltage control loop is further expressed as,

$$G_{uop}(s) = \frac{(k_{pv}s + k_{iv})(k_{pc}s + k_{ic})e^{-1.5sT_s}}{(Ls^2 + Rs + (k_{pc}s + k_{ic})e^{-1.5sT_s})Cs^2}. \quad (10)$$

Applying the first-order Taylor series expansion, the time delay can be approximated as,

$$e^{-1.5sT_s} = \frac{1}{1.5sT_s + 1}. \quad (11)$$

Based on Eq. (10) and Eq. (11), the closed-loop transfer function of the voltage control loop is given by,

$$G_{ucl}(s) = \frac{(k_{pv}s + k_{iv})(k_{pc}s + k_{ic})}{D(s)}, \quad (12)$$

where

$$D(s) = 1.5T_sLCs^5 + (1.5T_sRC + LC)s^4 + (RC + k_{pc}C)s^3 + (k_{ic}C + k_{pc}k_{pv})s^2 + (k_{pc}k_{iv} + k_{pv}k_{ic})s + k_{ic}k_{iv}. \quad (13)$$

Based on the open-loop transfer function $G_{uop}(s)$ in Eq. (10) of the Single-Input-Single-Output (SISO) closed-loop system in Figure 14, the system stability can be assessed by applying suitable stability criteria such as the Nyquist or the Routh–Hurwitz criterion to the closed-loop system characteristic equation that is given by,

$$1 + G_{uop}(s) = 0. \quad (14)$$

The Gain Margin (GM) and Phase Margin (PM) can be employed to determine the closed-loop stability from the open-loop transfer function of the nested control loop with given parameters that are designed according to the scaled power rating. Under the circumstance that GM and PM are positive, the stability is guaranteed provided that the magnitude and phase responses of the open-loop transfer function $G_{uop}(s)$ satisfy the following criteria,

$$\begin{cases} \text{GM} = 0 - 20\log(|G_{uop}(j\omega_{cp})|), & \text{GM} > 0, \\ \text{PM} = \angle G_{uop}(j\omega_{cg}) - (-180^\circ), & \text{PM} > 0, \end{cases} \quad (15)$$

where ω_{cg} is the gain crossover frequency at which the magnitude of $G_{uop}(s)$ is 0 dB, ω_{cp} is the phase crossover frequency at which the phase of $G_{uop}(s)$ crosses -180° .

Overall, this section presents the detailed GFI scaling-up procedures, the scale-up taxonomy of GFI and its associated components and control parameters variations, and their associated dynamic stability analysis. These details serve as a guideline for scaling up the power capability of individual GFIs specifically for pure simulation applications.

Figure 15: Simplified network for grid-forming control validation and black-start scenario.

Section B: GFI Power Scaling-up in PHIL Setups

This subsection presents the detailed procedures for scaling up the power of physical GFI that is incorporated into the PHIL setup by a current-type Ideal Transformer Model (ITM) interface. The power scale method is elaborated along with stability analysis of the PHIL setup with

power scale ratios. A case study is presented to reveal the impact of the power scale ratio on PHIL system stability. In addition, experimental validation results are further presented to demonstrate the efficacy of the scaling-up method in facilitating the GFI PHIL testing.

GFI establishes a stable and controllable voltage at its output terminal without the need for voltage angular synchronisation with the external grid, which enables the GFI to be a candidate for providing black-start services. Correspondingly, Figure 15 presents the circuit diagram of a sample scenario incorporating a voltage ramp of GFI to energise a network and synchronise with the main grid for black-start application. As discussed in (Feng, Alassi, et al., 2022; Alassi et al., 2023), a current-type ITM power interface is a feasible solution to incorporate a physical GFI into a PHIL closed-loop setup to energise the real-time emulated power network.

Figure 16 illustrates the equivalent circuit diagram of the PHIL setup comprising a real-time emulated power network, current-mode power amplifier, and power converter implemented with grid-forming control. Despite the feasibility of this interface to incorporate GFI in a PHIL setup, its practical implementation is constrained by the limited capability of the physical GFI in terms of its power rating. In practice, a laboratory-based GFI (typically on the kVA scale) is in a low power rating compared to the desired applications (e.g. MVA scale for black-start application). From an application point of view, proper power scaling is crucial for accurate replication of the behaviours of physical GFI to the real-time emulated grids that are hosted in RTDS.

Figure 16: A representation of the equivalent circuit diagram of a current-type PHIL system with a grid-forming inverter.

Figure 17: Equivalent model of the PHIL system with current-type ITM interface and GFI.

The equivalent model of the PHIL setup in Figure 16 is presented in Figure 17, of which the equivalent block-diagram is presented in Figure 18. As shown in Figure 18, the interface components, equivalent impedance, and interface signals are represented in the equivalent block diagram as a SISO closed-loop system. The scaling ratio design and the interfacing component modelling are presented below.

Figure 18: Equivalent block diagram of the I-ITM based PHIL system in Figure 17.

1. Scaling Ratio

The power capacity and voltage level of the network to be energised in RTDS is higher than that of the candidate GFI in the laboratory, and the current in the energised network is much higher than the current constraint of the current-mode power amplifier. As demonstrated in (Feng, Alassi, et al., 2022; Feng et al., 2021), voltage scaling ratio r_v is introduced to scale up the output voltage (V_H) of the physical GFI to a higher voltage ($V_{S'}$) in the emulated power network that is hosted in RTDS. Current ratio r_i is utilised to scale the digital current (I_S) in the power network down to a lower command for regulating the output current (I_H) of the power amplifier. The voltage ratio and current ratio are given by,

$$r_v = \frac{V_{S'nom}}{V_{Hnom}}, \quad r_i = \frac{I_{Hnom}}{I_{Snom}}, \quad \frac{S_S}{S_H} = \frac{r_v}{r_i}, \quad (16)$$

where V_H and $V_{S'}$ are the nominal voltage of the physical GFI and the emulated GFI on the RTDS side, respectively. I_H and I_S are the nominal current of the power amplifier and the rated current of the emulated power network on the RTDS side, respectively. S_H and S_S are the power rating of the physical GFI and the emulated GFI on the RTDS side, respectively.

2. Interface Modelling

From the system modelling point of view, the PHIL system is represented in the form of a SISO closed-loop system (Feng, Peña-Alzola, Syed, Norman, & Burt, 2022) and the respective equivalent model with all key components and interface signals are presented in Figure 17. The open-loop transfer function of this PHIL system as in Figure 18 is expressed as,

$$T_O(s) = r_v r_i \underbrace{G_1(s)G_2(s)G_3(s)G_4(s)}_{G_{PI}(s)} \frac{Z_H(s)}{Z_S(s)}, \quad (17)$$

where Z_S and Z_H are the equivalent impedance of the power network within the RTDS platform and the GFI equivalent impedance, respectively. $G_{PI}(s)$ is the transfer function of the power interface comprising the transfer functions of DAC card $G_1(s)$, power amplifier $G_2(s)$, voltage sensor $G_3(s)$, and ADC card in series with low-pass filter $G_4(s)$.

With the time delay τ in the PHIL closed-loop expressed by its equivalent Laplace transformer ($e^{-s\tau}$), the components in Eq. (17) are further modelled as,

$$\begin{cases} G_1(s) = k_1 e^{-sT_{d1}}, & G_2(s) = k_2 \frac{1}{\frac{s}{2\pi f_{c2}} + 1} e^{-sT_{d2}}, \\ G_3(s) = e^{-sT_{d3}}, & G_4(s) = \frac{1}{\frac{s}{2\pi f_{c4}} + 1} e^{-sT_{d4}}. \end{cases} \quad (18)$$

where k_1 and k_2 are the scaling factors of the DAC card and power amplifier, respectively. T_{d1} and T_{d4} represent the one time-step delay of RTDS, T_{d2} and T_{d3} are the time delay of the power amplifier and sensor, respectively. f_{c2} is the cut-off frequency of the power amplifier and f_{c4} is the equivalent cut-off frequency of the ADC anti-aliasing filter and LPF.

Based on the interface modelling and the open-loop transfer function of the SISO closed-loop PHIL system, Nyquist stability criteria can be applied to determine the closed-loop system stability by assessing the eigenvalues of the system characteristics equation ($1 + T_O(s) = 0$). Correspondingly, the system stability margins (e.g., GM and PM) as defined in Eq. (15) can be adapted to quantitatively assess the impact of the scaling ratios on the PHIL closed-loop system stability. This is crucial for designing an optimized scaling ratio according to the testing objectives with system stability guaranteed.

3. Scaling Ratio Assessment on PHIL Stability

The PHIL system parameters are tabulated in Table 8. According to the virtual circuit control theory as presented in (Vanassche, 2014), the output impedance of the physical Triphase 90 kVA (TP90 kVA) power converter operates in grid-forming mode is given by,

$$Z_H(s) = \frac{s5.5e^{-4} + 6.842}{s^25.5e^{-4} + s3.216e^{-4} + 1}. \quad (19)$$

The system open-loop transfer function in Eq. (17) can be calculated by utilising the system parameters in Table 8 and its corresponding frequency response is shown in Figure 19. The open-loop transfer function of the current-type PHIL setup with parameters in Table 8 has positive GM and PM, and the closed-loop setup is stable. The impact of the scaling ratios that are employed to facilitate the hardware GFI power rating and to limit the power amplifier current reference on the PHIL closed-loop stability is assessed. A higher power rating of the emulated GFI on the real-time simulation side can be achieved by implementing a high voltage scaling ratio. However, as illustrated in Figure 19, such a PHIL system can be unstable as the increment of the voltage ratio degrades the system gain margin. The cyan curve represents the PHIL system with the highest voltage ratio and power rating among the given systems. This PHIL system is unstable and presents negative GM and PM. The gain margin of the PHIL system is a factor by which the scaling ratio can be raised before breaching the system's stability. A stability assessment of the PHIL system with pre-designed scaling ratios is crucial prior to the final-stage system implementation.

4. Scaling Ratio Assessment on PHIL Operation

This section showcases the experimental validation results of the current-type ITM interface, focusing on its ability to scale up the power of a physical GFI and accurately represent it with a higher power rating in a real-time emulated power network within a PHIL setup. The effectiveness of the power scaling method is demonstrated by using the scaled GFI to energize a power network for the black start application. This experiment was undertaken in the Dynamic Power Systems Laboratory (DPSL) at the University of Strathclyde, Glasgow, UK.

Figure 20 illustrates the experimental setup, the cells of which correspond to that as presented in Figure 16. The simplified power network model is emulated in the RTDS, and the Triphase 90 kVA (TP90 kVA) power converter operates in grid-forming mode. These are coupled by a Triphase 15 kVA (TP15 kVA) power converter acting as a current-type power amplifier that sinks or sources current to the physical GFI (i.e., TP90 kVA converter), thus enabling the PHIL closed-loop configuration and mimicking the relative power behaviours in the emulated power network. The parameters of the emulated power network, power amplifier, and power converter are given in Table 8. The scaling ratios r_v and r_i as tabulated in Table 8 are employed to represent the

Figure 19: Bode diagram of the open-loop transfer function of current-type PHIL setup.

Figure 20: A representation of the experimental PHIL setup with physical grid-forming inverter.

power converter that is emulated in the RTDS with higher power rating and voltage levels than that of the actual GFI (TP90 kVA converter) and to scale down the RTDS reference current signal within the current constraint of the current-mode power amplifier (TP15 kVA converter), respectively. By doing so, the power rating of the emulated GFI at the RTDS side is 2062 (r_v/r_i) times that of the physical one (TP90 kVA converter).

To validate the effectiveness of the current-type PHIL interface and the associated power scaling method in realising stable and accurate testing of the hardware GFI integration throughout the black-start sequence, voltage-mode Virtual Synchronous Machine (VSM) control with a 5-second ramping time of the hardware GFI is utilised to realise a soft energisation of the power transformer together with the load connected at the PCC point in the emulated power network. The voltage and current at the interfacing point in RTDS, the output voltage of physical GFI (TP90 kVA converter), and the command and output current of current-mode power amplifier (TP15 kVA converter) are recorded by RTDS and Triphase datalogger, respectively, and are replotted by Matlab. Furthermore, the power of the physical GFI and the scaled-up power of the emulated GFI in RTDS is presented.

Table 8: PHIL setup parameters in Figure 16.

Description	Symbol	Value
PHIL setup		
Voltage scaling ratio	r_v	27.5
Current scaling ratio	r_i	0.0133
Cut-off frequency of $G_4(s)$ in Eq. (18)	f_{c4}	500 Hz
Transformer power rating (3 phase)	S_{Tx}	53 MVA
Transformer turns ratio (kV_{LLP}/kV_{LLS})	TR	11/33
Equivalent load in emulated power network	Z_{load}	54 Ω
Real-time digital simulator time step	τ_s	50 μs
Current-type power amplifier (TP15 kVA)		
DC voltage	V_{DC1}	650 V
Switching frequency	f_{sw1}	6.4 kHz
Sampling frequency	f_{s1}	6.4 kHz
Inverter side filter inductance	L_{11}	2.3 mH
Grid side filter inductance	L_{12}	0.93 mH
Filter capacitance	C_1	8.8 μF
PI controller proportional gain	k_p	11
PI controller integral gain	k_i	12.5
Hardware converter under test (TP90 kVA)		
DC voltage	V_{DC2}	700 V
Switching frequency	f_{sw2}	16 kHz
Sampling frequency	f_{s2}	16 kHz
Inverter side filter inductance	L_2	0.5 mH
Filter capacitance	C_2	47 μF
Emulated virtual resistance	R_e	6.8417 Ω
Emulated virtual inductance	L_e	0.05 mH

The voltage at the hardware GFI power converter output terminal is presented in Figure 21 with a zoomed section around the end of ramping time. This illustrates a successful hardware GFI output voltage tracking from 0 to its rated value without any measurable delay during the voltage ramp period. Furthermore, the voltage at the interfacing point of the real-time emulated power network in RTDS is illustrated in Figure 21. The scaled-up voltage at the interfacing point presents the same trend as the hardware GFI during the soft energisation with the voltage ramp period. Through the implementation of voltage scaling, the hardware GFI voltage behaviour is replicated in the emulated power network.

The current at the interfacing point of the real-time emulated power network in RTDS, as shown in Figure 22, is transmitted to the current-mode power amplifier as its command signal through proper scaling. Figure 22 present the command signal received from RTDS and the output current of the current-mode power amplifier (TP15 kVA converter), respectively. The scaled-down ($r_i = 0.0133$) three-phase current is accurately transmitted to TP15 kVA and is well-tracked by the output current of TP15 kVA. As shown in the zoomed version of the command and output

Figure 21: Experimental results of GFI output voltage and the representative digital voltage at the point of common coupling within the real-time emulated power network.

Figure 22: Experimental results of GFI output current and the representative digital current at the PCC within the real-time emulated power network.

Figure 23: Experimental results of GFI output power and the power injected at the point of common coupling within the real-time emulated power network.

current around the end of the ramping time, the actual output current exhibits a higher degree of harmonic content compared to the command signal. Although there are slight distortions in the output current, the phase alignment between the power amplifier output current and the command signal is maintained. This alignment is achieved through the implementation of a delay compensation method, which enables the replication of the current behaviour in the emulated power network by the power amplifier and its application to the hardware GFI.

Moreover, the scaled-up physical GFI output power and the actual power injected at the PCC within the real-time emulated power network are depicted in Figure 23. It is evident that the actual power injected at the PCC within the real-time emulated power network is well-tracked by the scaled-up physical GFI output power. This validates the efficacy of the power scaling ratios in achieving the intended power scale-up of a kVA GFI for MVA scale black-start applications within a stability-guaranteed PHIL closed-loop setup.

4.3 Scaling out of a Multi-Microgrid

As Micro Grid (MG) become more prevalent, there may be significant challenges for grid operators in terms of managing their operations and energy. To address this, the concept of microgrids - "micro" should be expanded to encompass a larger scale, where multiple microgrids can be interconnected to create a Multi-Microgrid (MMG) – 'mega' (MMG) system.

According to the definition provided in the literature, an MMG system is a high-level structure that operates at the medium voltage level, consisting of several low voltage microgrids, DERs, and consumers that are connected to nearby medium voltage feeders (Hatziaargyriou, 2014). In an MMG system, each MG can function as an active cell, offering flexibility to grid operators.

Typically, physical MGs have two interconnection types. The first type involves connecting MGs through the AC line using breakers. This type of connection is cost-effective with the right synchronisation algorithm. However, it presents a challenge for power management between MGs and is only suitable for MG systems that share the same frequency and voltage values across all MGs. The second type of interconnection involves using DC connections with Back-To-Back (BTB) converters, as shown in Figure 24 to interface between physical MGs. Implementing a hybrid microgrid topology with a DC connection at the BTB converter, as presented in (Majumder, 2014), could offer the advantage of integrating multiple AC and DC MGs at a single point. Furthermore, using BTB converters allows for independent control of each MG, resulting in a flexible MMG system with adjustable voltages and frequencies.

Therefore, this section presents the scaling-out approach for MGs systems with BTB converter interfaces.

4.3.1 Factors and Targets

The implementation of an MMG system is primarily motivated by the need to address the unstable operation of individual MGs during islanded mode and to provide numerous economic benefits to both the main grid and the participating MG systems. Typical examples of an MMG project are the PARADISE⁷ and m2M-GRID European project⁸. From these projects, it finds out that MMG systems offer several advantages for a resilient, sustainable, and cost-effective

⁷<https://anr.fr/Projet-ANR-13-PRGE-0007>

⁸<https://m2m-grid.eu>

Figure 24: Scaling-out scenario: Multi-microgrid system.

electricity supply by enabling the coordinated operation of individual networks. For instance, in islanded operations, MGs may experience fluctuations in Renewable Energy Source (RES), which can be mitigated by sharing controllable sources from other MGs. Therefore, in this subsection, as in Table 9, the factors and targets for scaling-out microgrids are defined based on the benefits for microsystems.

Table 9: Factors and Targets for scaling-out microgrids.

Target	Factor	Scale Range	Unit
Micro system (Frequency enhancing)	Number of microgrids	1 - 4	unit

4.3.2 Energy Router Interface

In the scaling-out approach, microgrids system are replicated and interconnected. By implementing microgrids or localized power generation systems, power systems can be scaled out by decreasing dependence on centralised generation and improving the robustness and dependability of electricity provision. The interface among them can be the energy router, and its topology for an MMG system with 2 MGs is presented in Figure 25. As can be seen in the figure, the selected energy router topology involves two types of MGs, namely grid-forming MGs and grid-following MGs. To ensure the energy router operates effectively, the MMG system necessitates the presence of at least one grid-forming MG. The grid-forming unit is determined as the MG within the MMG system that possesses the highest controllable energy. For this particular case, it is assumed that MG_j , accompanied by a Voltage Source Controller (VSC) (VSC_j), serves as the grid-forming unit, while MG_k , along with VSC_k , functions as the grid-following unit. The control functionalities of the associated VSCs within the energy router can be defined as follows:

- VSC's function for grid-forming MGs: the VSC operating in this mode is responsible for supplying energy to the other MGs and regulating the DC voltage in the ER's common link.
- VSC's function for grid-following MGs: in this operational mode, the responsibility of the VSC in the microgrid is to effectively track the control signals of the P/Q references provided by the control system.

The detail of mathematical models for these VSC control function in the energy router is presented in the reference (Pham et al., 2020).

Figure 25: Interfaces among microgrids.

4.3.3 Demonstration through Frequency Enhancing

The micro-system for the scaling-out approach is described through a 4 MGs system with an energy router (see Figure 26). The MMG system comprises four AC MGs that have the capability to connect or disconnect from the primary power grid. An energy router with the DC-link, equipped with a capacitor, is utilised to interconnect all the MGs.

Figure 26: Multi-microgrid system with 4 microgrids

The MMG multi-frequency regulation strategy implemented for MGs' frequency enhancing relies on a droop frequency control characteristic (Yoo, Nguyen, & Kim, 2017), (Pham, Tran, Hably, & Bacha, 2021), illustrated in Figure 27. In this setup, MG_j is assigned to regulate the DC voltage, while its frequency is supported by MG_k . Under normal conditions, MG_j operates at frequency A_j , whereas MG_k operates at frequency A_k . When there is a load change in MG_j , its operating point shifts to B_j following its droop characteristic. To address this increased load, MG_k can assist MG_j by transferring energy through the ER interface. Consequently, the frequency of MG_j recovers from point B_j to C_j , while the frequency of MG_k decreases from A_k to

C_k . This trade-off is inherent in the method. Once the normalised frequencies (f_n) of both MGs become equal, the system frequencies of MG_j and MG_k stabilise at new steady-state values (C_j and C_k). It is worth noting that the control function of the grid-forming converter unit in this part aligns with the one presented in Figure 25.

Figure 27: Strategy for droop frequency control between microgrids.

The control diagram of the grid following converter in this part is shown in Figure 28, which includes the P/Q controller with the multi-microgrid frequency function and the current controller. The detail of the multi-microgrid frequency calculation function is presented as follows:

$$f_{n-i} = \begin{cases} \frac{(f_i - f_{i, \text{rated}})}{(f_{i, \text{max}} - f_{i, \text{rated}})}, & (f_i > f_{i, \text{rated}}) \\ \frac{(f_i - f_{i, \text{rated}})}{(f_{i, \text{rated}} - f_{i, \text{min}})}, & (f_{i, \text{rated}} > f_i) \end{cases} \quad (20)$$

where, f_i represents the measured frequency of MG_i ; $f_{i, \text{rated}}$ is the rated frequency of MG_i ; $f_{i, \text{max}}$ and $f_{i, \text{min}}$ are the maximum and minimum frequency deviations, respectively; f_{n-i} is the normalised frequency of MG_i .

Figure 28: The control diagram of the grid following microgrid for multi-frequency control.

For the purpose of explanation, this case study focuses only on MG_1 and MG_4 . In this sense, MG_1 is responsible for controlling the DC-link, while MG_4 operates in P/Q mode. Nevertheless, it is presumed that MG_1 has reached its limit in maintaining the voltage of the DC-link. As a result, its frequency has dropped to a critical value and cannot return to the standard value. By exchanging grid information with MG_4 , it is ensured that MG_4 will engage the frequency coordination mode exclusively when the frequency of MG_1 reaches a critical value of 49.8 Hz. In this simulation scenario, the minimum and maximum frequency values for both MG_1 and MG_4 are equal: $f_{1,max} = f_{4,max} = 50.2$ Hz; $f_{1,min} = f_{4,min} = 49.8$ Hz.

The simulation results are presented in Figure 29. At time points $t = 2.5$ s and $t = 3.5$ s, additional loads are introduced to MG_1 . Thanks to the DC-link isolation, from $t = 0$ s to $t = 3.5$ s, the frequency disturbances in MG_1 do not affect MG_4 within the MMG system. Only when the frequency of MG_1 drops to 49.8 Hz at $t = 3.5$ s the frequency coordination mode is activated. Consequently, the load in MG_1 is identified and shared with MG_4 through the ER interface, resulting in the restoration of MG_1 's frequency to an acceptable value as in Figure 29 (d). By introducing a multi-frequency control system, the limitations of single-frequency control have been effectively addressed. This scaling-out approach compensates for power fluctuations across all MGs.

Figure 29: Scaling-out simulation validation: frequencies droop approach.

4.4 Scaling out: Inter-Operation of multiple OLTC Transformers

In order to analyse the effect of multiplicity in a distribution network, the reference system in Figure 9 was also employed. In this case, two scenarios named *parallel* and *sequential* were considered, but only the former was simulated due to its straight implementation.

For this purpose, Figure 30 depicts the overview of the two defined scenarios in a broader

configuration, i.e., in a distribution network where an HV/MV power transformer feeds several MV/LV distribution transformers, as usual, but with the difference that each of them has the capability of regulating voltage through its own OLTC controller. However, under this scenario, the dilemma posed is, what if there are too many OLTCs distributed in the same network? Which one of them will have priority to operate? Will the network operator notice any conflict between them?

To deal with these questions, it was assumed that the network in Figure 30 can be divided into two sub-circuits to define the *parallel* and *sequential* operation of the OLTC transformers, as shown in Figure 31a and 31b.

Figure 30: Scaling-out Scenario.

Figure 31: Sub-circuits derived from Figure 30.

In regard to the *parallel* case, the original OLTC transformer from Figure 9 was replaced with the OLTC transformers OLTC2 and OLTC3 depicted in Figure 31a to operate in parallel. For this case, the voltage step per tap parameter of each OLTC controller was divided by two in order to keep a similar variation ratio.

From the simulation results, Figure 32 compares the tap changer operation for the original case

with one OLTC transformer with respect to two distribution transformers connected in parallel, each one with an OLTC controller. It can be seen that the operation of both OLTC controllers gives similar results when the system is scaled-out. The mismatch between both curves is due to the quasi-dynamic simulation runs with a different time resolution.

Figure 32: OLTC parallel operation.

On the other hand, implementing two OLTCs transformers operating *sequentially* can introduce several issues in the distribution network, such as:

- **Voltage fluctuations:** As each transformer adjusts its tap position independently, it can result in sudden changes in voltage levels, provoking these fluctuations to affect the stability and performance of the distribution network.
- **Synchronization:** Synchronizing the tap-changing operations of two transformers can be challenging because both transformers need to change their taps simultaneously to maintain proper voltage regulation. Any mismatch or delay in synchronization can lead to voltage imbalances or transient disturbances in the network.
- **Control complexity:** Implementing sequential operation of OLTC transformers requires sophisticated control systems. Coordinating the actions of both transformers and ensuring proper sequencing and timing of tap changes can be complex. The control logic needs to be carefully designed and implemented to avoid conflicts and ensure smooth operation.
- **Communication and coordination:** Effective communication and coordination between the two transformers are crucial. They need to exchange information about their tap positions, voltage levels, and load conditions to make appropriate decisions for tap changes. Establishing reliable communication links and protocols between the transformers can be a challenge, especially if they are located at a distance from each other.
- **Fault identification and troubleshooting:** In case of any fault or malfunction in either of the transformers, identifying the source of the issue and troubleshooting becomes more complex when multiple transformers are involved. Isolating and diagnosing problems in the sequential operation setup requires advanced monitoring and diagnostic systems.

5 Case Study on Domain Expansion and Scaling in a Multi-Energy System Case

Narrative: A multi-utility is planning a local renewable energy community where a heat pump can increase the self-supply of heat in the area while, at the same time, the weak grid must be accounted for. The proposed solution is a power-limiting voltage control that will limit the consumption of the heat pump in cases of end-of-feeder low-voltage (or grid high demand). The energy community objective is also to supply as much heat as possible locally from the available PV generation. A buffer tank at the heat pump is meant to ensure available heat supply under congested situations and to enable the heat pump to operate when PV production is available and to supply the heat from the tank when the heat pump is not operating.

This case raises engineering concerns regarding multi-domain interactions where solving voltage and congestion issues will affect the operation of the heating plant and vice versa.

In this study case, a quantitative analysis of two engineering concerns is considered:

1. Which interactions between the two domains are significant and need to be accounted for in the control design and sizing?
2. To what extent can the tank size contribute to a) mitigating voltage problems and b) maximising the self-consumption of renewable energy in the area?

The two concerns raised in these scenarios are the subject of the following two case studies. The first is a case of “domain expansion” analysis and the second is a case of “scaling up”.

The outlined numerical analyses will be performed on the basis of a benchmark simulation model. This case is based on a benchmark of a co-simulation scenario involving both electricity and district heating infrastructure, where the coupling is established through a district-level heat pump. The benchmark applied in this section and presented in Figure 33 is available here (*ERIGrid2/benchmark-model-multi-energy-networks: v1.0*, 2021) and also described in (*D-JRA1.1 Benchmark Scenarios*, 2022) and paper (Widl, Wild, Heussen, Rikos, & Hoang, 2022).

Note: The presented results are an illustration of the approach with a numerical model, the presented results are only illustrative of the methods applied and have no bearing on the considered application domain.

The final section will then present how the results can be used to identify physical laboratory testing needs for preparing the field roll-out of the design.

5.1 Analysis of Inter-domain Causality and Sensitivity

Which interactions between the two domains are significant and need to be accounted for in the control design and sizing?

In order to identify the important inter-domain interactions (ref. question 1 above), the first applied method is an One (factor)-at-a-Time (OAT) sensitivity analysis. For smaller scenarios, it would also be possible to directly start with a Global Sensitivity Analysis (GSA) method, but for GSA a quite large sample size is needed and with the multi-energy benchmark the

Figure 33: Multi-energy benchmark (ERIGrid2/benchmark-model-multi-energy-networks: v1.0, 2021).

execution time would be too high⁹. While in a GSA combinations of all factor variations would be simulated, in the OAT approach, as the name says, only one factor at a time is changed and fewer simulation runs are needed.

It allows to define the scenario in a JSON file and does sampling and analysis of the results based on the scenario definition and is available in an open repository¹⁰. The configuration contains all factors, which should be used for variations and the range or distribution for each of them. A more detailed description of the toolbox can be found in (*D-JRA1.2 Methods for Holistic Test Reproducibility*, 2023). In the example shown here, one simulation is run with the standard configuration of all parameters as baseline and then every factor is varied to the minimum and maximum of its defined range. The effect of these three simulation runs per factor is analysed based on the effect these changes have on the target metrics (see Table 10 for a list of target metrics). In Figure 34 this is exemplarily shown for the impact of the factors on the target metric *average Coefficient of Performance (COP) of the heat pump*.

Table 10: Target metrics for Case 5: Interaction between two domains.

Target Metric	Unit
Maximum voltage bus 2	p.u.
Maximum line loading line 0	%
Heat pump average COP	
Self-consumption electricity	MWh
Minimum supply temperature (Critical node temperature)	°C
Imported heat	GWh

⁹A single simulation run takes approx. 15 min.

¹⁰https://github.com/ERIGrid2/toolbox_doe_sa

Figure 34: One (factor)-at-a-Time (OAT) analysis for target metric average COP of the heat pump.

To get a better overview of the impact one factor has overall, a ranking is calculated, as shown in Figure 35. For that, the factors are sorted for each target metric based on the variance of their three simulation runs. This analysis bases only on a small sample size and only the direct impacts can be investigated, but it can still support the user in the decision of which factors should be further investigated and which might be negligible. It has also to be stated, that the process requires domain expertise, as the results are sensitive to changes of the available parameter ranges. Thus, it might also be an iterative process to find the right ranges, which make sense for SA.

For further investigation, there are different foci: (1) *design parameters* can be examined, which are interesting from an engineering point of view; (2) *scenario parameters* can be examined, which might be important for upscaling. From the *scenario parameters*, especially, the heat profile and PV scaling and the power of the heat pump are interesting for further investigation as the OAT SA showed a high impact. The most impact was shown for the consumer load scaling, which was not further analysed here as the effect is technically similar to the PV scaling. From the *design parameters*, the inner diameter of the hot water tank and the minimum operating point of the heat pump and the proportional term K_p of the voltage controller are further investigated.

To get a deeper knowledge about the impact of the chosen factors on the target metrics, a

Figure 35: Ranking of the impact of factors overall target metrics.

(a) Sobol indices for maximum voltage at bus 2 of the electricity grid

(b) Sobol indices for heat import from the external grid

Figure 36: Sobol indices for different target metrics resulting from sampling of design parameters.

GSA was conducted. For the implementation in the toolbox the SALib¹¹ was used (Herman & Usher, 2017; Iwanaga, Usher, & Herman, 2022), which provides multiple sampling and analysis approaches. For sampling the quasi-random sobol method was used. The simulation results were analysed based on the target metrics listed in Table 10 with the sobol indices approach (Saltelli et al., 2010). The sensitivity measure (first order sensitivity coefficient) S_i and the total effect index S_{Ti} , which measures the first and higher order effects (interactions), were calculated and are depicted in Figure 36 and 38 (in the Figures, S1 represents the first order effect S_i and ST the total effect S_{Ti}). These indices show the effect variations of the factor have on the target metrics and allow to order of the factors based on their effect. Additionally, the confidence of the result is calculated for a confidence interval of 95% and shown by the black

¹¹<https://salib.readthedocs.io/en/latest/index.html>

lines.

The three factors chosen for design parameters were used for the calculation of sobol indices and the results are depicted in Figure 36. In the analysis, we focus here on the first-order effect (blue bars) and can see that the diameter of the hot water tank and the proportional term K_p of the voltage controller have the most impact on the bus voltage (see Figure 36a), while the heat import to the external grid is mainly influenced by the minimum operating point of the heat pump (see Figure 36b). As the effect of two parameters is more interesting, we want to further investigate the effect on the bus voltage and do a new simulation run with variations of these two parameters and use the meta-model approach for analysis. In Figure 37, the two factors are shown on the x- and y-axis and the target metric on the z-axis. It can be seen, that the inner diameter has more impact on the target metric compared to the proportional term K_p of the voltage controller.

Figure 37: Impact of the factors inner diameter of the hot water tank and proportional term K_p of the voltage controller on the maximum voltage at bus 2 based on the meta-modeling approach.

(a) Sobol indices for self-consumption of electricity.

(b) Sobol indices for critical node temperature of heat grid.

Figure 38: Sobol indices for different target metrics resulting from sampling of scenario parameters.

The three factors chosen for scenario parameters were used for the calculation of sobol indices and the results are depicted in Figure 38. It can be seen that the electricity self-consumption is mainly affected by the scaling of PV, partly by the power of the heat pump and to a lesser extent by the heat profile scaling (see Figure 38a), while the effect of the PV scaling is almost negligible for the critical node temperature and the other two have more influence (see Figure

38b). Since the PV scaling parameter is only seen to influence one of the two targets, the factors selected for further analysis are heat pump-rated power and heat profile scaling. A meta-model for each of the two targets is illustrated in Figure 39. It can be seen, that the power of the heat pump has a more direct effect on the self-consumption of electricity than the heat profile scaling (see Figure 39a), while it is the other way around for the critical node temperature (see Figure 39b).

Figure 39: Impact of the factors heat profile scaling and heat pump power on two target metrics based on the meta-model approach.

5.2 Tank Size Scaling Problem Analysis

In this section, the same multi-energy benchmark simulation scenario as in the previous section is used as a base. But here the focus is not on domain extension sensitivity screening, but on illustrating a potential scaling analysis using a meta-modelling approach. This approach can be extended to optimisation, as presented in (Zaibi et al., 2018). A component of the scenario which is suitable for scaling is the Hot Water Tank (HWT). The tank volume can be parameterised by height and inner diameter, of which only the inner diameter is used in the following, with the height fixed at $7.9m$. We start the analysis with just the inner diameter of the HWT – varied between 1 and 8 meters, equivalent to approx. $620l$ - $40.000l$. Assuming an operating temperature difference of 10 Kelvin, an HP-rated capacity of $100kW$, this corresponds to approximately $1min$ to $9h$ of full thermal load capacity storage. The results are depicted in Figure 40 and show different effects. For the voltage (see Figure 40a) and self-consumption (see Figure 40c) the impact of the inner diameter seems quite high for an inner diameter smaller than 2 meter¹². For larger sizes, there is still a slightly positive impact for enlarging the HWT¹³. For the average COP of the heat pump an optimum can be seen around 5 meter inner diameter ($3.5h$) as depicted in Figure 40b, while the critical node temperature benefits from an increasing diameter, which begins to saturate around a diameter of 10 meters (see Figure 40d). These results could suggest conclusions to be already drawn for the scaling of the HWT size. However, the

¹²Given the very short equivalent full load time of this storage in the range below 5 minutes, and the third-digit scale of the variation, this effect may be a simulation artefact.

¹³The HP control strategy is simple as it operates with a fixed temperature setpoint - a larger effect on self-consumption can be expected in this range with a suitable control strategy.

scaling of the HWT size can also be influenced by other scaling effects. Thus, we analyse also the scaling of the HWT together with other scaling factors.

Figure 40: Impact of variations in the inner diameter of the HWT to four target metrics.

Analysis of the factors *inner diameter of HWT* together with *scaling of the PV systems* is shown in Figure 41. The relative impact of PV on both the voltage and self-consumption of the PV scaling seems to significantly exceed the size HWT scaling, illustrated by the trends shown in Figure 40. Here no consistent effect of the tank size is recognisable. For the average COP and the critical node temperature the effect of PV system scaling seems to be not significant and the shape is similar to Figure 40. The tendency from the SA in the previous section is confirmed here, as Figure 38b shows that the PV scaling has almost no impact on the critical node temperature, while the inner diameter has at least some impact.

The wavy effects in the meta-models, highly visible in the average COP in Figure 40b, have not been fully explained, but are recognizable as modelling artefacts. A hypothesis to be investigated further: the chosen order of the meta-model, along with the discretisation effects of the simulation model used here.

The results of simulation with varied factors inner diameter of HWT and heat profile scaling are shown in Figure 42. It can be seen, that the heat profile scaling seems to have less impact on the voltage and the self-consumption, the same trends as shown for the one-factor analysis in Figure 40 are visible. The tendency from the Sensitivity Analysis in the previous section are confirmed here, as Figure 38b shows that the heat profile scaling has significantly more impact on the critical node temperature than the PV scaling. The impact of the inner diameter seems

Figure 41: Impact of variations in the inner diameter of the HWT and scaling of the PV systems to four target metrics.

to be still stronger, but there is at least some impact of the heat profile scaling visible.

The same analysis was performed for scaling the line length of line 0 of the electricity grid. As the effect is similar for the PV scaling, the results are omitted here.

The meta-models derived here can be considered a first iteration for identifying the significant interactions that should be accounted for in a sizing design.

As presented in (Zaibi et al., 2018), such DoE based meta-models, can be suitable for simplifying optimisation problems in complex plants. Considering these results, several, but not all investigated parameters should be considered in a corresponding optimisation setup. The optimisation could capture the dependency of HP average COP and the minimum supply temperature. Also, lower-order meta-models should be considered to approximate the simulation data sets.

Considering the design question posed at the outset: *To what extent can the tank size contribute to a) mitigating voltage problems and b) maximising the self-consumption of renewable energy in the area?*, it has to be concluded that the model does not identify a significant cou-

Figure 42: Impact of variations in the inner diameter of the HWT and scaling of the heat profile systems to four target metrics.

pling between tank size and the stated target metrics. It remains to be investigated whether a modification of the applied current control strategy would yield different results.

5.3 Toward Laboratory and Field Testing of Multi-Domain Energy Systems

The results from the simulative analysis should provide indications to identify physical laboratory testing needs for preparing the field roll-out of the design. Given the practical results, a revision of the control strategy would be the most promising first step.

Since in laboratory experiments the run-time is typically limited both the time spans and the number of samples will be significantly reduced. Many parameters will be fixed by the available equipment.

Here the factor and target analysis needs to be repeated and applied to the laboratory setup.

The first scope of such analysis would be to test and improve the individual component model parameters and assumptions. A second scope would be to characterise and validate the predictions of the combined model. If the control strategy gets revised, a physical scaling of the control system parameters to the laboratory equipment would be meaningful, potentially reducing experiment time for the integrated system test.

Other factors do not reveal much discrimination, such as `voltage_ctrl_k_p`. Such factors need to be investigated further in lab experiments, also since their influence is sensitive to the components' dynamics. A lab test for factors of the control system can prepare the field deployment in that it identifies reasonable parameter ranges for tuning the control system.

6 Conclusions

Scaling a small-scale monolithic energy system is a straightforward process, primarily involving traditional power plants. However, challenges arise when it comes to the development of smart grids and CPES due to the involvement of variable elements such as DERs. Existing infrastructures may not be able to support high penetration of DERs, and therefore, it is essential to consider the testing method in order to address the impacts of scaling and domain expansion.

Scalability and replicability are often used interchangeably, but they serve different purposes. Scalability refers to a system's capacity to modify its scale in order to accommodate increasing demand volumes, whereas replicability refers to the quality of a system that allows for the creation of a copy of it at a different time or place. The modernization of energy systems requires testing and validation for seamless integration between components and systems, as well as future capabilities for scalability and domain expansion. In a digitalized energy system, two common vectors of domain extension are the reliance ICT and the sourcing of flexibility. One of the main challenges for researchers is how to extend the capability of an existing testbed to integrate new components and other domains. Considering foreseeable changes in energy systems, such as real-time communication and sector coupling, scaling methods and domain extension become important for researchers and practitioners to effectively validate solutions that are interdependent with other domains.

This research work introduces approaches for testing and validation in physical and simulated testbeds, supporting technology scaling strategies, namely scaling up and scaling out. Both strategies aim to increase the system's capability but from different perspectives. A scale-up approach focuses on improving the performance of an individual system, such as increasing the physical size or rating of a component. On the other hand, scaling out is focused on improving the overall capacity and reliability of a distributed system, which involves increasing the number of components or units. This report discussed the adoption of these strategies from an ICT background to energy systems. A range of analytical methods to support testing and validation efforts with the different types of scaling was identified and summarised.

In order to illustrate the application of these new scaling concepts, two sets of case studies are presented. The two case studies utilise reference benchmarks developed in previous work of the ERIGrid 2.0 project:

1. Case Studies for Power System Scaling Up and Out, and
2. Case Study on Domain Expansion and Scaling up in a Multi-Energy System.

The first set of case studies focuses on scaling up and scaling out in power systems, specifically in the context of the low voltage network with high DERs penetration. Examples include scaling up OLTC and GFI, as well as the impact of scaling out on MG towards MMG systems. The second set of case studies focuses on the multi-energy network, which is becoming increasingly prominent in the energy system, particularly with regard to sector coupling. This case study demonstrates the technical challenges involved in integrating heat networks (i.e., domain expansion) and how to prepare for controlling them (i.e., scaling up).

There is a significant potential for consolidating the presented approaches, as well as further studies to explore applications and combinations of the concepts and analytical methods. In particular use cases discussing applications with the integration ICT scaling aspects should be considered. These studies could examine the balance between scaling up and scaling out strategies. Interested users can apply the concepts and practical examples presented in this

document to a wide range of scaling scenarios, including increasing the flexibility of simulation models and enhancing existing and new testbeds to support scaling and domain expansion capabilities in preparation for the design of field roll-out.

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